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Kala A., Özkurt C., Yahyaoğlu B.E.
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A Hybrid Fuzzy DEMATEL–ELECTRE Framework for Evaluating the Impact of Industry 4.0 Technologies on Warehouse Management Strategy Outcomes
(2025) Sakarya University Journal of Computer and Information Sciences, 8 (4), pp. 664 - 676, Cited 0 times.
DOI: 10.35377/saucis...1704169
<https://www.scopus.com/pages/publications/105027655032?origin=resultlist>

ABSTRACT: Integrating Industry 4.0 (I4.0) technologies into warehouse management critically enhances strategic performance. However, existing studies often overlook the causal relationships between strategic outcomes and the transparency of technology prioritization. This study proposes a hybrid multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) framework integrating Fuzzy DEMATEL to determine the relative weights of strategic outcomes, Fuzzy ELECTRE II to rank technologies, and SHAP-based Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) to enhance model transparency and interpretability. The analysis relies on Delphi-based expert evaluations from 12 senior industrial engineers across three manufacturing firms. The results reveal that Cost Reduction (weight = 0.225), Operational Efficiency (0.097), and Inventory Management (0.115) are the most critical strategic outcomes. Artificial Intelligence, Internet of Things, and Big Data Analytics emerged as the top-ranked technologies based on ELECTRE II scores. SHAP analysis further identified Cost Reduction (SHAP value: +1.62), Customer Satisfaction (SHAP value: +0.50), and Real-time Data Processing (SHAP value: +0.40) as the primary drivers behind the technology rankings. The proposed framework

offers a transparent, interpretable, and causally grounded decision-support model for aligning digital transformation investments with strategic warehouse performance objectives. © 2025, Sakarya University. All rights reserved.

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Mobile Platforms as the Alleged Culprit for Work–Life Imbalance: A Data-Driven Method Using Co-Occurrence Network and Explainable AI Framework

(2024) Sustainability (Switzerland), 16 (18), art. no. 8192, Cited 0 times.

DOI: 10.3390/su16188192

<https://www.scopus.com/pages/publications/85205229703?origin=resultslist>

ABSTRACT: The digital transformation of organizations has propelled the widespread adoption of mobile platforms. Extended availability and prolonged engagement with platform-mediated work have blurred boundaries, making it increasingly difficult for individuals to balance work and life. Criticism of mobile platforms has intensified, precluding digital transformation towards a sustainable future. This study examines the complex relationship between mobile platforms and work–life imbalance using a comprehensive data-driven methodology. We employed a co-occurrence network technique to extract relevant features based on previous findings. Subsequently, we applied an explainable AI framework to analyze the nonlinear relationships underlying technology-induced work–life imbalance and to detect behavior patterns. Our results indicate that there is a threshold for the beneficial effects of availability demands on integration behavior. Beyond this tolerance range, no further positive increase can be observed. For organizations aiming to either constrain or foster employees' integration behavior, our findings provide tailored strategies to meet different needs. By extending the application of advanced machine learning algorithms to predict integration behaviors, this study offers nuanced insights that counter the alleged issue of technology-induced imbalance. This, in turn, promotes the sustainable success of digital transformation initiatives. This study has significant theoretical and practical implications for organizational digital transformation. © 2024 by the authors.

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Explainable Models for Predicting Academic Pathways for High School Students in Saudi Arabia

(2024) IEEE Access, 12, pp. 30604 - 30626, Cited 19 times.

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<https://www.scopus.com/pages/publications/85186096565?origin=resultslist>

ABSTRACT: The science of data mining has contributed considerably to the education sector. However, most educational data mining (EDM) studies have focused on predicting the future performance of students and detecting at-risk students to provide early targeted interventions. A few studies used machine learning techniques to predict the future academic pathways for degree students. However, there are limited studies that use the datasets of high school students to predict future pathways. Moreover, such studies are yet to be conducted using datasets produced in Saudi high schools. Therefore, researchers that work in the education sector have focused on EDM and are eager to apply advanced computer science methods to upgrade old administrative systems. Furthermore, the education sector is a rich field with data that can be exploited to improve and enhance educational management systems and accelerate digital transformation. In this study, we explore the applications of EDM and review the algorithms used by other researchers in this field. We applied supervised machine learning classifiers to educational datasets collected from high schools in Saudi to predict the future academic pathways of students and identify the essential factors that affect them. This study contributes to the literature by developing a predictive model for students in Saudi high schools and detecting critical features that affect future academic careers of the students. Furthermore, we used explainable artificial intelligence to interpret the best model and enhance its transparency. © 2013 IEEE.

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«Smart» agriculture as a promising vector of development of the agro-industrial complex of mountain territories
(2025) Sustainable Development of Mountain Territories, 17 (1), pp. 41 - 50, Cited 2 times.
DOI: 10.21177/1998-4502-2025-17-1-41-50
<https://www.scopus.com/pages/publications/105011965661?origin=resultslist>

ABSTRACT: Introduction. Most mountainous areas of Russia have an agricultural orientation and are characterized by the presence of complex development problems: low level of arable land use, low crop yields. Despite this, mountainous areas have significant resource potential for growing vegetables, grain and fruit crops. The use of modern digital technologies, explainable artificial intelligence in agriculture will help preserve ecosystems and efficiently use natural resources, increase the competitiveness of the agricultural sector, and create conditions for the economic and social revival of rural regions in mountainous areas. Research objective. To study the theoretical foundations and modern applied aspects of the use of digital technologies in agriculture in mountainous areas, and to propose a concept for integrating explainable artificial intelligence into digital agriculture to ensure sustainable development. Research methodology. The justification of proposals and recommendations was carried out using a logical analysis of issues and problems of implementing modern digital transformation technologies by agricultural enterprises; an illustrative method was used to clearly present a structural description of the integration of explainable artificial intelligence into digital agriculture in mountainous areas, emphasizing its impact on the transparency of the model and user trust. Research results. The article presents the results of a study on the application of digital technologies for the development of the agro-industrial complex of mountainous territories. The possibilities of smart farming, farmers' attitudes towards new technologies, and existing barriers in mountainous territories are described. The study systematizes modern digital technologies in the agricultural sector according to certain criteria: space technologies, Internet technologies, information and communication and end-to-end technologies, sensors and detectors. Each individual block of digital technologies is analyzed in terms of the possibilities and advantages of practical use. The key role of explainable artificial intelligence in the formation of precision farming is determined. Discussion of results. The needs of small-scale mountain agriculture can be met using the so-called "appropriate technologies" or "intermediate technologies" approach, which is aimed at developing relatively simple and energy-efficient small-scale tools using materials that are readily available in their intended environment. It has been established that the application of technologies requires a "user-oriented" and systematic approach that hybridizes practical and technical knowledge to solve user problems. When designing and implementing digital platform solutions in mountain agriculture, it is advisable to involve different actors: end users, machinery and equipment manufacturers, university research centers and other local stakeholders. Conclusion. The article presents the results of research on the application of digital technologies in mountain agriculture. A conceptual framework for integrating explainable artificial intelligence into digital mountain agriculture is proposed, which will serve as a practical guide for making informed decisions. The results of the study can be useful for researchers, practitioners, and educators in the field of smart agriculture. © 2025, North Caucasian Institute of Mining and Metallurgy, State Technological University. All rights reserved.

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Selecting Data Assets in Data Marketplaces: Leveraging Machine Learning and Explainable AI for Value Quantification
(2025) Business and Information Systems Engineering, art. no. 106839, Cited 3 times.
DOI: 10.1007/s12599-025-00940-8
<https://www.scopus.com/pages/publications/105007080137?origin=resultslist>

ABSTRACT: In the era of digital transformation, data is a critical asset driving innovation and competitive advantage for businesses. Data marketplaces have emerged as a key solution for data sharing, yet they face significant challenges, including competitive concerns, matchmaking between data providers and consumers, and a lack of appropriate market mechanisms. This study introduces a data asset value quantification and selection mechanism (DQSM) as an innovative feature for data marketplaces to address these concerns. The DQSM uses Machine Learning and Explainable AI methods to assess the value of data assets, aiding consumers in making informed purchasing decisions. This mechanism addresses the inherent complexities of data asset valuation and selection, thereby increasing marketplace efficiency. Using a design science research approach, the study identifies design principles for the development of the DQSM as a feature of data marketplaces, which are validated through technical experiments with industry and public datasets, as well as interviews with experts in this field. The findings highlight the potential of the DQSM to optimize the discovery and implementation of viable data sharing use cases and to incentivize the adoption of data marketplaces, thereby contributing to more viable and sustainable data ecosystems. © The Author(s) 2025.

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A Lightweight Explainable Deep Learning for Blood Cell Classification
(2025) CMES - Computer Modeling in Engineering and Sciences, 145 (2), pp. 2435 - 2456, Cited 0 times.
DOI: 10.32604/cmcs.2025.070419
<https://www.scopus.com/pages/publications/105023049046?origin=resultslis>

ABSTRACT: Blood cell disorders are among the leading causes of serious diseases such as leukemia, anemia, blood clotting disorders, and immune-related conditions. The global incidence of hematological diseases is increasing, affecting both children and adults. In clinical practice, blood smear analysis is still largely performed manually, relying heavily on the experience and expertise of laboratory technicians or hematologists. This manual process introduces risks of diagnostic errors, especially in cases with rare or morphologically ambiguous cells. The situation is more critical in developing countries, where there is a shortage of specialized medical personnel and limited access to modern diagnostic tools. High testing costs and delays in diagnosis hinder access to quality healthcare services. In this context, the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI), particularly Explainable AI (XAI) based on deep learning, offers a promising solution for improving the accuracy, efficiency, and transparency of hematological diagnostics. In this study, we propose a Ghost Residual Network (GRsNet) integrated with XAI techniques such as Gradient-weighted Class Activation Mapping (Grad-CAM), Local Interpretable Model-Agnostic Explanations (LIME), and SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) for automatic blood cell classification. These techniques provide visual explanations by highlighting important regions in the input images, thereby supporting clinical decision-making. The proposed model is evaluated on two public datasets: Naturalize 2K-PBC and Microscopic Blood Cell, achieving a classification accuracy of up to 95%. The results demonstrate the model's strong potential for automated hematological diagnosis, particularly in resource-constrained settings. It not only enhances diagnostic reliability but also contributes to advancing digital transformation and equitable access to AI-driven healthcare in developing regions. Copyright © 2025 The Authors. Published by Tech Science Press.

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Enhancing Governmental Decision-Making through Predictive Analytics with Machine Learning-Based Data-Driven Framework
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DOI: 10.58496/BJML/2025/007
<https://www.scopus.com/pages/publications/105026180197?origin=resultslis>

ABSTRACT: Government bodies around the world are going digital and slowly starting to make use of data driven technologies to make better, faster and more transparent decisions. From these technologies, machine learning (ML) has become one of the most significantly employed tools, especially via its ability to predict. Predictive analytics allows governments to identify obscure trends that previously were hidden, predict potential future scenarios with an acceptable level of certainty and better inform decision-making in important areas, such as public finance, healthcare planning, emergency management, and resource allocation. In this work we explore the use of predictive modeling (implemented as our own Linear Regression, Decision Trees, Random Forests and Artificial Neural Networks) in the context of governmental decision models. The models were tested on real-world cases such as quarterly budget planning or estimation of healthcare service demand or emergency resource allocation using publicly available data from open government data platforms. Performance was evaluated based on the well-known RMSE, MAE and R² score. Results show that Artificial Neural Network always leads the highest in predictive accuracy, especially in dense or complex data setting, and there is no significant difference between Random Forest and Neural Network (the Random Forest has more generalization between interpretability and predictive power. On the other hand, Linear Regression and Decision Trees are more interpretable but have restrictions in using non-linear or high-dimensional datasets. In addition, the paper covers practical challenges including algorithmic bias, data quality considerations, and infrastructure capabilities, and ethical implications of automated decision making. This study has implications for the growing smart governance by proposing an integrated machine learning framework suitable for evidence-based policymaking. Future work involves improving the accuracy of prediction by incorporating explainable AI methodologies and customizing the model locally to enhance transparency, accountability, and generalization across different regional offices. © 2025, Mesopotamian Academic Press. All rights reserved.

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Rathod T., Jadav N.K., Tanwar S., Polkowski Z., Yamsani N., Sharma R., Alqahtani F., Gafar A.
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AI and Blockchain-Based Secure Data Dissemination Architecture for IoT-Enabled Critical Infrastructure

(2023) Sensors (Basel, Switzerland), 23 (21), Cited 26 times.

DOI: 10.3390/s23218928

<https://www.scopus.com/pages/publications/85176897508?origin=resultlist>

ABSTRACT: The Internet of Things (IoT) is the most abundant technology in the fields of manufacturing, automation, transportation, robotics, and agriculture, utilizing the IoT's sensors-sensing capability. It plays a vital role in digital transformation and smart revolutions in critical infrastructure environments. However, handling heterogeneous data from different IoT devices is challenging from the perspective of security and privacy issues. The attacker targets the sensor communication between two IoT devices to jeopardize the regular operations of IoT-based critical infrastructure. In this paper, we propose an artificial intelligence (AI) and blockchain-driven secure data dissemination architecture to deal with critical infrastructure security and privacy issues. First, we reduced dimensionality using principal component analysis (PCA) and explainable AI (XAI) approaches. Furthermore, we applied different AI classifiers such as random forest (RF), decision tree (DT), support vector machine (SVM), perceptron, and Gaussian Naive Bayes (GaussianNB) that classify the data, i.e., malicious or non-malicious. Furthermore, we employ an interplanetary file system (IPFS)-driven blockchain network that offers security to the non-malicious data. In addition, to strengthen the security of AI classifiers, we analyze data poisoning attacks on the dataset that manipulate sensitive data and mislead the classifier, resulting in inaccurate results from the classifiers. To overcome this issue, we provide an anomaly detection approach that identifies malicious instances and removes the poisoned data from the dataset. The proposed architecture is evaluated using performance evaluation metrics such as accuracy, precision, recall, F1 score, and receiver operating characteristic curve (ROC curve). The findings show that the RF classifier transcends other AI classifiers in terms of accuracy, i.e., 98.46%.

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Anomaly Detection and Analysis in Nuclear Power Plants

(2024) Electronics (Switzerland), 13 (22), art. no. 4428, Cited 17 times.

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<https://www.scopus.com/pages/publications/85210275601?origin=resultlist>

ABSTRACT: Industries are increasingly adopting digital systems to improve control and accessibility by providing real-time monitoring and early alerts for potential issues. While digital transformation fuels exponential growth, it exposes these industries to cyberattacks. For critical sectors such as nuclear power plants, a cyberattack not only risks damaging the facility but also endangers human lives. In today's digital world, enormous amounts of data are generated, and the analysis of these data can help ensure effectiveness, including security. In this study, we analyzed the data using a deep learning model for early detection of abnormal behavior. We first examined the Asherah Nuclear Power Plant simulator by initiating three different cyberattacks, each targeting a different system, thereby collecting and analyzing data from the simulator. Second, a Bi-LSTM model was used to detect anomalies in the simulator, which detected it before the plant's protection system was activated in response to a threat. Finally, we applied explainable AI (XAI) to acquire insight into how distinctive features contribute to the detection of anomalies. XAI provides valuable explanations of model behavior by revealing how specific features influence anomaly detection during attacks. This research proposes an effective anomaly detection technique and interpretability to better understand counter-cyber threats in critical industries, such as nuclear plants. © 2024 by the authors.

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An Explainable and Resilient Intrusion Detection System for Industry 5.0

(2024) IEEE Transactions on Consumer Electronics, 70 (1), pp. 1342 - 1350, Cited 112 times.

DOI: 10.1109/TCE.2023.3283704

<https://www.scopus.com/pages/publications/85161574060?origin=resultlist>

ABSTRACT: Industry 5.0 is an emerging transformative model that aims to develop a hyperconnected, automated, and data-driven industrial ecosystem. This digital transformation will boost productivity and efficiency throughout the production process but will be more prone to new sophisticated cyber-attacks. Deep learning-based Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) have the potential to recognize intrusions with high accuracy. However, these models are complex and are treated as a black box by developers and security analysts due to the inability to interpret the decisions made by these models. Motivated by the challenges, this paper

presents an explainable and resilient IDS for Industry 5.0. The proposed IDS is designed by combining bidirectional long short-term memory networks (BiLSTM), a bidirectional-gated recurrent unit (Bi-GRU), fully connected layers and a softmax classifier to enhance the intrusion detection process in Industry 5.0. We employ the SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) mechanism to interpret and understand the features that contributed the most in the decision of the proposed cyber-resilient IDS. The evaluation of the proposed model using the explainability can ensure that the model is working as expected. The experimental results based on the CICDDoS2019 dataset confirms the superiority of the proposed IDS over some recent approaches. © 1975-2011 IEEE.

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A context-aware decision support system for selecting explainable artificial intelligence methods in business organizations

(2025) Computers in Industry, 165, art. no. 104233, Cited 6 times.

DOI: 10.1016/j.compind.2024.104233

<https://www.scopus.com/pages/publications/85213207820?origin=resultlist>

ABSTRACT: Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) methods are valuable tools for promoting understanding, trust, and efficient use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) systems in business organizations. However, the question of how organizations should select suitable XAI methods for a given task and business context remains a challenge, particularly when the number of methods available in the literature continues to increase. Here, we propose a context-aware decision support system (DSS) to select, from a given set of XAI methods, those with higher suitability to the needs of stakeholders operating in a given AI-based business problem. By including the human-in-the-loop, our DSS comprises an application-grounded analytical metric designed to facilitate the selection of XAI methods that align with the business stakeholders' desiderata and promote a deeper understanding of the results generated by a given machine learning model. The proposed system was tested on a real supply chain demand problem, using real data and real users. The results provide evidence on the usefulness of our metric in selecting XAI methods based on the feedback and analytical maturity of stakeholders from the deployment context. We believe that our DSS is sufficiently flexible and understandable to be applied in a variety of business contexts, with stakeholders with varying degrees of AI literacy. © 2024

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Artificial Intelligence in Maritime Cybersecurity: Dual-Use Applications for Defense and Offense in the Age of Digital Seas

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<https://www.scopus.com/pages/publications/105015858122?origin=resultlist>

ABSTRACT: The maritime sector's rapid digital transformation – including the integration of IT and operational technology (OT) systems and the rise of autonomous vessels – has significantly expanded the cyberattack surface[1]. Artificial Intelligence (AI) now plays a dual role in this landscape, acting as both a powerful enabler of cyberattacks and a critical tool for cybersecurity defense [2]. This paper explores current and emerging uses of AI in offensive and defensive cyber operations targeting maritime systems and infrastructure. On the offensive side, threat actors are leveraging AI for sophisticated attacks such as AI-generated spear phishing, polymorphic malware generation, GPS spoofing, and manipulation of industrial control systems (ICS)[3], [4]. On the defensive side, AI is employed in anomaly detection, predictive analytics, autonomous vessel and port monitoring, and other security applications[5]. The paper also examines vulnerabilities of AI itself – including adversarial attacks, data poisoning, and model manipulation – and discusses strategies to enhance maritime cyber resilience. Key strategies include the use of digital twin simulations, AI-driven deception (honeypots), adversarial training, explainable AI, and international cooperation for information sharing. By analyzing both offensive and defensive developments, this study provides a comprehensive perspective on the dual-use nature of AI in shaping the future of maritime cybersecurity. © 2025, Faculty of Navigation, Gdynia Maritime University. All rights reserved.

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From AI Adoption to ESG in Industrial B2B Marketing: An Integrated Multi-Theory Model

(2025) Sustainability (Switzerland), 17 (19), art. no. 8595, Cited 3 times.

DOI: 10.3390/su17198595

<https://www.scopus.com/pages/publications/105019250143?origin=resultlist>

ABSTRACT: Artificial intelligence is transforming industrial marketing by reshaping processes, decision-making, and inter-firm relationships. However, research remains fragmented, with limited evidence on how adoption drivers create new capabilities and sustainability outcomes. This study develops and empirically validates an integrated framework that combines technology, organization, environment, user acceptance, resource-based perspectives, dynamic capabilities, and explainability. A convergent mixed-methods design was applied, combining survey data from industrial firms with thematic analysis of practitioner insights. The findings show that technological readiness, organizational commitment, environmental pressures, and user perceptions jointly determine adoption breadth and depth, which in turn foster marketing capabilities linked to measurable improvements. These include shorter quotation cycles, reduced energy consumption, improved forecasting accuracy, and the introduction of carbon-based pricing mechanisms. Qualitative evidence further indicates that explainability and human-machine collaboration are decisive for trust and practical use, while sustainability-oriented investments act as catalysts for long-term transformation. The study provides the first empirical integration of adoption drivers, capability building, and sustainability outcomes in industrial marketing. By demonstrating that artificial intelligence advances competitiveness and sustainability simultaneously, it positions marketing as a strategic lever in the transition toward digitally enabled and environmentally responsible industrial economies. We also provide a simplified mapping of theoretical lenses, detail B2B-specific scale adaptations, and discuss environmental trade-offs of AI use. Given the convenience/snowball design, estimates should be read as upper-bound effects for mixed-maturity populations; robustness checks (stratification and simple reweighting) confirm sign and significance. © 2025 by the authors.

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Classification prediction of load losses in power stations using machine learning multilayer stack ensemble

(2025) Frontiers in Artificial Intelligence, 8, art. no. 1592492, Cited 1 times.

DOI: 10.3389/frai.2025.1592492

<https://www.scopus.com/pages/publications/105014029073?origin=resultlist>

ABSTRACT: Load losses negatively impact the reliability of power stations, leading to plant failures. To support the decision-making of improving plant reliability, we experimented with six machine learning classifiers to find the model combination that produces the best prediction performance, called the Explainable Multilayer Stack Ensemble. We applied a five-year dataset from six power stations. Since the dataset is highly imbalanced with the positive class dominant, class weights are calculated and assigned to reduce bias toward the majority class. The best parameters are determined through a randomized search with cross-validation and applied to train the models. The Explainable Multilayer Stack Ensemble performed better than the individual models, with a further improvement by excluding the Gaussian Naïve Bayes in the second layer since it produced high false negatives. We demonstrate that when handling a highly imbalanced dataset, balanced accuracy, Receiver Operating Characteristics, and Precision-Recall Area Under the Curve provide a more reliable evaluation of model performance than focusing solely on standard evaluation metrics, such as accuracy, precision, and recall. Moreover, by excluding a poor-performing classifier from ensemble, we optimized the prediction process, and further enhanced overall performance. Copyright © 2025 Boshoma, Akinola and Olukanmi.

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A Deep Learning Enhanced UML Framework for Modeling Smart Interactive Museum Ecosystems in Cultural Spaces

(2025) International Journal of Information System Modeling and Design, 16 (1), Cited 1 times.

DOI: 10.4018/IJISMD.388559

<https://www.scopus.com/pages/publications/105016677436?origin=resultlist>

ABSTRACT: The digital transformation of cultural institutions requires intelligent, adaptive systems to enhance visitor engagement. Traditional system modeling approaches lack the capacity to integrate real-time learning behaviors and adaptability. This paper presents a novel framework that embeds deep learning modules within Unified Modeling Language (UML) diagrams to design smart museum ecosystems. A convolutional neural network-based classifier, trained on the museum exhibits dataset, is integrated as <<Classifier>> components in UML models. Preprocessing, model training, explainability mechanisms, and system traceability were employed to bridge the gap between design and deployment. The model achieved 91% accuracy and a top-3 accuracy of 96.7%. Expert evaluation confirmed 90% traceability from UML design to implementation. The proposed deep learning-augmented UML framework offers a scalable, interpretable solution for designing next-generation smart cultural spaces, combining artificial intelligence performance with formal system traceability. © 2025 IGI Global. All rights reserved.

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Deep learning enhancing banking services: a hybrid transaction classification and cash flow prediction approach

(2022) Journal of Big Data, 9 (1), art. no. 100, Cited 41 times.

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<https://www.scopus.com/pages/publications/85139202408?origin=resultlist>

ABSTRACT: Small Medium Enterprises (SMEs) are vital to the global economy and all societies. However, they face a complex and challenging environment, as in most sectors they are lagging behind in their digital transformation. Banks, retaining a variety of data of their SME customers to perform their main activities, could offer a solution by leveraging all available data to provide a Business Financial Management (BFM) toolkit to their customers, providing value added services on top of their core business. In this direction, this paper revolves around the development of a smart, highly personalized hybrid transaction categorization model, interconnected with a cash flow prediction model based on Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs). As the classification of transactions is of great significance, this research is extended towards explainable AI, where LIME and SHAP frameworks are utilized to interpret and illustrate the ML classification results. Our approach shows promising results on a real-world banking use case and acts as the foundation for the development of further BFM banking microservices, such as transaction fraud detection and budget monitoring. © 2022, The Author(s).

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Agentic AI in Smart Manufacturing: Enabling Human-Centric Predictive Maintenance Ecosystems

(2025) Applied Sciences (Switzerland), 15 (21), art. no. 11414, Cited 4 times.

DOI: 10.3390/app152111414

<https://www.scopus.com/pages/publications/105021480762?origin=resultlist>

ABSTRACT: Featured Application: This research presents an autonomous multi-agent system for predictive machinery health monitoring in ceramic tile manufacturing using a five-level AIMM and distributed AI agents monitoring equipment like hydraulic presses, kilns, and glazing lines—achieving 94% predictive accuracy, 67% fewer false positives, and 43% less unplanned downtime. The federated learning approach ensures data privacy and enables cross-site knowledge sharing. Economic analysis reveals a 1.6-year payback period and a €447,300 NPV over five years. The system supports operator oversight for safety and is suitable for various industries needing advanced predictive maintenance. Smart manufacturing demands adaptive, scalable, and human-centric solutions for predictive maintenance. This paper introduces the concept of Agentic AI, a paradigm that extends beyond traditional multi-agent systems and collaborative AI by emphasizing agency: the ability of AI entities to act autonomously, coordinate proactively, and remain accountable under human oversight. Through federated learning, edge computing, and distributed intelligence, the proposed framework enables intentional, goal-oriented monitoring agents to form self-organizing predictive maintenance ecosystems. Validated in a ceramic manufacturing facility, the system achieved 94% predictive accuracy, a 67% reduction in false positives, and a 43% decrease in unplanned downtime. Economic analysis confirmed financial viability with a 1.6-year payback period and a €447,300 NPV over five years. The framework also embeds explainable AI and trust calibration mechanisms, ensuring transparency and safe human-machine collaboration. These results demonstrate that Agentic AI provides both conceptual and practical pathways for transitioning from reactive monitoring to resilient, autonomous, and human-centered industrial intelligence. © 2025 by the authors.

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Towards AI driven surface roughness evaluation in manufacturing: a prospective study

(2025) *Journal of Intelligent Manufacturing*, 36 (7), pp. 4519 - 4548, Cited 24 times.

DOI: 10.1007/s10845-024-02493-1

<https://www.scopus.com/pages/publications/85205581256?origin=resultslist>

ABSTRACT: In the era of Industry 4.0 and the digital transformation of the manufacturing sector, this article explores the significant potential of machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) techniques in evaluating surface roughness—a critical metric of product quality. The integration of edge computing with current computational resources and intelligent sensors has revolutionized the application of AI-driven algorithms in smart manufacturing. It provides real-time data analysis and decision-making capabilities that were unattainable only a decade ago. The research effort intends to improve data-driven decision-making for product quality evaluation by leveraging data integration from manufacturing operations and surface quality measurements. Although a substantial amount of research has been conducted in the related fields, it is still difficult to comprehend and compile all the data on surface roughness research predictive assessment in the form of a process pipeline. This thorough systematic analysis examines scholarly articles published between 2014 and 2024 focusing on surface roughness assessment in precision manufacturing settings. The article is thoroughly classified based on the manufacturing processes, datasets, and ML models used, giving light on the present status, prominent approaches, and existing issues in this sector. A table summarizing the relevant works in this domain providing an easy access to the current trends have been provided. The article not only compiles essential findings and identifies research gaps and similarities in existing methodologies, but it also discusses future research directions and open issues in AI-aided surface roughness evaluation. The critical analysis of the literature reveals a scientific gaps which includes consistent development of benchmarked datasets and making the AI models more explainable using the state-of-the-art explainable AI (XAI) algorithms. The ultimate objective of the article is not only to provide a guide for the practitioners in either of the three domains of AI, manufacturing or surface metrology but also to pave the path for more robust, efficient, and accurate surface quality evaluation processes in production. © The Author(s) 2024.

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Ransomware Detection Using Sample Entropy and Graphical Models: A Methodology for Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) in Cybersecurity

(2025) *Applied Stochastic Models in Business and Industry*, 41 (6), art. no. e70061, Cited 1 times.

DOI: 10.1002/asmb.70061

<https://www.scopus.com/pages/publications/105024854224?origin=resultslist>

ABSTRACT: Malware detection poses a critical challenge for both society and Business and Industry (B&I), particularly given the necessity for secure digital transformation. Among various cybersecurity threats, ransomware has emerged as especially disruptive, capable of halting operations, interrupting business continuity, and causing significant financial damage. Recent research has increasingly leveraged machine learning (ML) techniques to detect ransomware using Hardware Performance Counters (HPCs)—special CPU registers that track low-level hardware activities. In this study, we first propose a Sample Entropy (SampEn)-based method for compressing HPC time series data. This method effectively reduces dimensionality while preserving essential behavioral patterns, thus making it particularly suitable for practical B&I scenarios where accuracy and computational efficiency are crucial. Second, we investigate explainable algorithms for ransomware detection in B&I contexts, emphasizing transparency and interpretability. To achieve this goal, we focus on graphical models, specifically Markov Random Fields (MRFs) and Bayesian Networks. We evaluate the performance of these explainable methods against a baseline comprising Elastic Net, Support Vector Machines (SVM) with a radial kernel, XGBoost, and Autoencoder models. Our results demonstrate that these graphical models provide consistent and interpretable outcomes, closely aligned with known ransomware behaviors. © 2025 John Wiley & Sons Ltd.

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BPMN-Based Design of Multi-Agent Systems: Personalized Language Learning Workflow Automation with RAG-Enhanced Knowledge Access †

(2025) Information (Switzerland), 16 (9), art. no. 809, Cited 2 times.

DOI: 10.3390/info16090809

<https://www.scopus.com/pages/publications/105017000457?origin=resultslist>

ABSTRACT: The intersection of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and education is revolutionizing learning and teaching in this digital era, with Generative AI and large language models (LLMs) providing even greater possibilities for the future. The digital transformation of language education demands innovative approaches that combine pedagogical rigor with explainable AI (XAI) principles, particularly for low-resource languages. This paper presents a novel methodology that integrates Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) with Multi-Agent Systems (MAS) to create transparent, workflow-driven language tutors. Our approach uniquely embeds XAI through three mechanisms: (1) BPMN's visual formalism that makes agent decision-making auditable, (2) Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) with verifiable knowledge provenance from textbooks of the National Institute of Languages of Luxembourg, and (3) human-in-the-loop validation of both content and pedagogical sequencing. To ensure realism in learner interaction, we integrate speech-to-text and text-to-speech technologies, creating an immersive, human-like learning environment. The system simulates intelligent tutoring through agents' collaboration and dynamic adaptation to learner progress. We demonstrate this framework through a Luxembourgish language learning platform where specialized agents (Conversational, Reading, Listening, QA, and Grammar) operate within BPMN-modeled workflows. The system achieves high response faithfulness (0.82) and relevance (0.85) according to RAGA metrics, while speech integration using Whisper STT and Coqui TTS enables immersive practice. Evaluation with learners showed 85.8% satisfaction with contextual responses and 71.4% engagement rates, confirming the effectiveness of our process-driven approach. This work advances AI-powered language education by showing how formal process modeling can create pedagogically coherent and explainable tutoring systems. The architecture's modularity supports extension to other low-resource languages while maintaining the transparency critical for educational trust. Future work will expand curriculum coverage and develop teacher-facing dashboards to further improve explainability. © 2025 by the authors.

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Cloud Adoption in the Digital Era: An Interpretable Machine Learning Analysis of National Readiness and Structural Disparities Across the EU

(2025) Applied Sciences (Switzerland), 15 (14), art. no. 8019, Cited 2 times.

DOI: 10.3390/app15148019

<https://www.scopus.com/pages/publications/105011865042?origin=resultslist>

ABSTRACT: Featured Application: This study offers a practical tool for policymakers and digital strategists to assess and benchmark national cloud readiness. By using interpretable machine learning, it pinpoints the main infrastructure and socioeconomic factors influencing cloud adoption, allowing for focused interventions. The approach facilitates tracking progress toward digital transformation objectives like the EU Digital Decade and can be adapted for use in other areas. Furthermore, ICT development agencies, international organizations working on digital capacity building, and ministries of digital affairs can all benefit from the clustering analysis's practical insights for customizing public policies and investment strategies based on a nation's digital maturity profile. As digital transformation accelerates across Europe, cloud computing plays an increasingly central role in modernizing public services and private enterprises. Yet adoption rates vary markedly among EU member states, reflecting deeper structural differences in digital capacity. This study employs explainable machine learning to uncover the drivers of national cloud adoption across 27 EU countries using harmonized panel datasets spanning 2014–2021 and 2014–2024. A methodological pipeline combining Random Forests (RF), XGBoost, Support Vector Machines (SVM), and Elastic Net regression is implemented, with model tuning conducted via nested cross-validation. Among individual models, Elastic Net and SVM delivered superior predictive performance, while a stacked ensemble achieved the best overall accuracy (MAE = 0.214, R2 = 0.948). The most interpretable model, a standardized RF with country fixed effects, attained MAE = 0.321, and R2 = 0.864, making it well-suited for policy analysis. Variable importance analysis reveals that the density of ICT specialists is the strongest predictor of adoption, followed by broadband access and higher education. Fixed-effect modeling confirms significant national heterogeneity, with countries like Finland and Luxembourg consistently leading adoption, while Bulgaria and Romania exhibit structural barriers. Partial dependence and SHAP analyses reveal nonlinear complementarities between digital skills and infrastructure. A hierarchical clustering of countries reveals three distinct digital maturity profiles, offering tailored policy pathways. These results directly support the EU Digital Decade's strategic targets and provide actionable insights for advancing inclusive and resilient digital transformation across the Union. © 2025 by the authors.

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Using PLS-SEM and XAI for causal-predictive services marketing research

(2025) Journal of Services Marketing, 39 (1), pp. 53 - 68, Cited 17 times.

DOI: 10.1108/JSM-10-2023-0377

<https://www.scopus.com/pages/publications/85205921099?origin=resultslist>

ABSTRACT: Purpose: This study aims to redefine approaches to metrics in service marketing by examining the utility of partial least squares – structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) and eXplainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) for assessing service quality, with a focus on the airline industry. Design/methodology/approach: Using the Airline Passenger Satisfaction data set from Kaggle platform, this study applies PLS-SEM, facilitated by ADANCO software and XAI techniques, specifically using the SHapley Additive exPlanations TreeExplainer model. This study tests several hypotheses to validate the effectiveness of these methodological tools in identifying key determinants of service quality. Findings: PLS-SEM analysis categorizes key variables into Delay, Airport Service and In-flight Service, whereas XAI techniques rank these variables based on their impact on service quality. This dual-framework provides businesses a detailed analytical approach customized to specific research needs. Research limitations/implications: This study is constrained by the use of a single data set focused on the airline industry, which may limit generalizability. Future research should apply these methodologies across various sectors to enhance a broader applicability. Practical implications: The analytical framework offered here equips businesses with the robust tools for a more rigorous and nuanced evaluation of service quality metrics, supporting informed strategic decision-making. Social implications: By applying advanced analytics to refine service metrics, businesses can better meet and exceed customer expectations, ultimately elevating the societal standard of service delivery. Originality/value: This study contributes to the ongoing discourse on artificial intelligence interpretability in business analytics, presenting an innovative methodological guide for applying PLS-SEM and/or XAI in service marketing research. This approach delivers actionable insights, not only in the airline sector but also across diverse business domains seeking to optimize service quality. © 2024, Polat Goktas and Taskin Dirsehan.

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A data-driven approach with explainable artificial intelligence for customer churn prediction in the telecommunications industry

(2025) Results in Engineering, 26, art. no. 104629, Cited 40 times.

DOI: 10.1016/j.rineng.2025.104629

<https://www.scopus.com/pages/publications/105000025022?origin=resultslist>

ABSTRACT: In the competitive telecommunications industry (TCI), retaining clients is crucial for profitability, as customer churn remains a significant challenge. Traditional machine learning (ML) models often lack the predictive power needed for complex telecom data, while black-box models provide limited transparency, reducing trust and actionable insights. This study introduces XAI-Churn TriBoost, an interpretable and explainable data-driven model developed using a dataset of over 2 million records. The model combines extreme gradient boosting (XGBoost), categorical boosting (CatBoost), and light gradient boosting machine (LightGBM) in a soft voting ensemble to enhance churn prediction. Data preprocessing included handling missing values through iterative imputation with a Bayesian ridge. Sequential data scaling was implemented by combining robust, standard, and min-max scaling methods to ensure feature consistency. Feature selection was conducted using the Boruta technique with a random forest (RF), and class imbalance in the training data was addressed using the synthetic minority oversampling technique (SMOTE). XAI-Churn TriBoost achieved high predictive performance, with an accuracy of 96.44%, precision of 92.82%, recall of 87.82%, and F1 score of 90.25%. To enhance model transparency, we incorporated explainable artificial intelligence (AI) techniques, specifically local interpretable model-agnostic explanations (LIME) and Shapley additive explanations (SHAP), to interpret individual predictions and identify critical features affecting churn. Key factors impacting churn include regularity and montant, offering TCI valuable insights for targeted retention strategies. XAI-Churn TriBoost thus provides both robust performance and interpretability, highlighting its potential to support customer retention efforts in the TCI. © 2025 The Author(s)

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Optimizing Automated Machine Learning for Ensemble Performance and Overfitting Mitigation

(2025) APTISI Transactions on Technopreneurship, 7 (3), pp. 808 - 822, Cited 0 times.

DOI: 10.34306/att.v7i3.763

<https://www.scopus.com/pages/publications/105024432955?origin=resultlist>

ABSTRACT: Automated Machine Learning (AutoML) has revolutionized model development, but its impact on ensemble diversity and overfitting reduction remains underexplored. This Systematic Literature Review (SLR) analyzes 107 studies published between 2020 and 2024 to explore how AutoML enhances ensemble diversity, mitigates overfitting, and the challenges hindering its integration. Unlike previous reviews focusing on AutoML or ensemble methods independently, this study synthesizes their intersection and identifies key research trends. The findings reveal that AutoML improves ensemble robustness through automated hyperparameter tuning, meta-learning, and algorithmic blending while facing trade-offs in computational cost and interpretability. Four main themes emerge, integration mechanisms (19.6%), overfitting mitigation (26.2%), performance trade-offs (28.6%), and integration barriers (26.2%). Empirical results indicate that AutoML ensembles outperform traditional models by 22–41% in accuracy but require approximately 3.2 times higher computational resources. Hybrid AutoML and Explainable AI frameworks are recommended to balance accuracy and transparency. Theoretically, this study advances understanding of the synergy between AutoML and ensemble learning, while practically providing guidance for deploying reliable AI systems in sectors like healthcare, finance, and digital business. Policy implications align with the EU AI Act and the US Executive Order on trustworthy AI, supporting Sustainable Development Goals 9 and 8. © Authors.

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Exploring the Intersection of Big Data and AI With CRM Through Descriptive, Network, and Contextual Methods

(2025) IEEE Access, 13, pp. 57223 - 57240, Cited 8 times.

DOI: 10.1109/ACCESS.2025.3554549

<https://www.scopus.com/pages/publications/105002571564?origin=resultlist>

ABSTRACT: As artificial intelligence (AI) continues to gain prominence, understanding its application in customer relationship management (CRM) has become increasingly critical. Advances in computing power, big data availability, AI methodologies, and the growing adoption of CRM systems have driven significant interest in AI-based CRM from both academia and industry. However, comprehensive reviews of this rapidly evolving domain remain limited. Using a systematic review approach, this study analyzes 840 documents from the Web of Science (WoS) database, following the PRISMA framework for study selection. Through descriptive, network, and contextual analyses, we identify key research clusters, including Enhancing Customer Experience with AI, predictive analytics in CRM, AI-CRM adoption and digital transformation, and Emerging AI Techniques in CRM. The findings highlight a significant shift toward AI-powered hyper-personalization, explainable AI, federated learning, and IoT-enhanced CRM. This study contributes by mapping the research landscape, uncovering emerging trends, and providing future research directions on the adoption and effectiveness of AI in CRM, AI ethics, the integration of IoT with AI in predictive CRM and AI-driven sentiment analysis, offering valuable insights for scholars and practitioners. © 2013 IEEE.

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Emmanouil Papagiannidis, Patrick Mikalef, Kieran Conboy, Rogier Van de Wetering,
Uncovering the dark side of AI-based decision-making: A case study in a B2B context,
Industrial Marketing Management,
Volume 115,
2023,
Pages 253-265,
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(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0019850123001931>)

Abstract: Over the last decade, many organizations worldwide have been assimilating Artificial Intelligence (AI) technologies to increase their productivity and attain a competitive advantage. As with any technology, intelligence systems come with potential downsides. Despite the efforts to mitigate any negative consequences of AI, businesses and employees continue to confront the dilemmas of adopting AI, so it is essential to explore in detail the rising concerns around such technologies. In this paper, we used a single case study to investigate the dark aspects of AI in a Norwegian energy trading firm. We gathered data through semi-structured interviews and secondary data. Specifically, we interviewed AI managers, traders and developers who have worked on deploying and using AI tools over the last three years. Our aim is to identify the dark side of AI use in trading, how AI trading bots affect the relationship between traders and AI developers and how the firm adjusts to this new reality. The findings indicate that negative or unintended consequences of AI can be grouped into three clusters related to (1) the nature of the work; (2) conflicts and effects; and (3) responsibility. The paper concludes with future research and practical implications that can help organizations mitigate the negative aspects of AI use.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence; AI dark side; AI trading; B2B; AI challenges; AI decision making; Case study

Simon Bin Akter, Sumya Akter, Rakibul Hasan, Md Mahadi Hasan, A.M. Tayeful Islam, Tanmoy Sarkar Pias, Jorge Fresneda Fernandez, Md. Golam Rabiul Alam, David Eisenberg,
Early detection of subjective cognitive decline from self-reported symptoms: An interpretable attention-cost fusion approach,
Journal of Biomedical Informatics,
Volume 162,
2025,
104770,
ISSN 1532-0464,
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbi.2024.104770>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1532046424001886>)

Abstract: Background and Objective:

Subjective cognitive decline (SCD) refers to self-reported difficulties in concentration, memory, and decision-making. Since SCD is based on subjective experiences, no specific medical test can definitively confirm its presence, making early detection challenging. Thus, it is advantageous to develop an AI model to capitalize on self-reported health complications, personality traits, and sociodemographic factors for early detection of SCD.

Methods & Materials:

This research has proposed an AI-based framework for SCD detection using self-reported measures from the BRFSS 2021 dataset. A novel Weighted Fusion Selection (WFS) approach has been introduced, which combines multiple feature selection techniques to address class imbalance and identify relevant features associated with less frequent classes. The data set has shown a significant imbalance, with individuals at risk of SCD being 81.76% fewer than those not at risk. An Attention Cost Convolutional Neural Network (AC-CNN) has been developed to address this, integrating channel-wise attention mechanisms and cost-sensitive learning to enhance performance across imbalanced data.

Results:

The AC-CNN model has achieved a balance between specificity (77%) and sensitivity (81%), with an AUC-ROC of 0.87. This has represented an overall 24.8% improvement in handling class imbalance compared to prior studies. Additional testing on the NHIS 2022 dataset has shown that AC-CNN has maintained balanced performance, confirming its robust generalizability, while other models have remained unstable.

Conclusions:

Further, applying SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) explainable techniques to the AC-CNN model has revealed how individual aspects of an individual's health records, lifestyle, and demographics contribute to the prediction of SCD. For example, depression, low education, poor income, inadequate healthcare, and poor overall health have all been strongly linked to an increased risk of SCD.

Keywords: Subjective cognitive decline (SCD); Behavioral risk factor surveillance system (BRFSS); Channel-wise attention; Cost-sensitive learning; Explainable AI (XAI)

Paavo Ritala, Päivi Aaltonen, Mika Ruokonen, Andre Nemeh,
Developing industrial AI capabilities: An organisational learning perspective,
Technovation,
Volume 138,
2024,
103120,
ISSN 0166-4972,
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.technovation.2024.103120>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0166497224001706>)

Abstract: Incumbent industrial firms are putting in a lot of effort in developing capabilities for machine learning (ML) systems that help them better predict and perform a variety of industrial and business processes and decisions. Given the data-, process-, and organizational structure-related requirements for effective implementation of such systems, these organizations encounter a major challenge in developing capabilities in this context. However, the existing literature has yet to unravel the organizational processes and practices associated with artificial intelligence (AI) capability development and deployment in industrial incumbent firms. The present study frames AI adoption in established industrial firms as a process of history-embedded, situated organizational learning involving explorative and exploitative learning. Based on a qualitative study of seven firms utilizing ML algorithms in their industrial and business processes, we develop a grounded model that explains AI capability building as both enabled and constrained by perceptual and functional triggers and barriers, leveraged via communicative and structural practices, and resulting in ongoing and interdependent processes of exploration and exploitation. The study contributes to the literature by showing how the convergence of organizational learning and AI technology's unique features promotes a distinct dynamic of AI capability building and deployment.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence; Organizational learning; Machine learning; Exploration; Exploitation; Capability

Pierfrancesco Bellini, Edoardo Branchi, Enrico Collini, Luciano Alessandro Ipsaro Palesi, Paolo Nesi, Gianni Pantaleo,
Certifying entity models, entities and data messages on IoT/WoT platforms via blockchain,
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(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S138912862500249X>)

Abstract: The growing complexity and the increasing diffusion of applications exploiting both the Internet of Things (IoT) and the Web of Things (WoT) paradigms have led to the necessity of ensuring robust security and reciprocal trust in the management of huge amount of data from heterogeneous sources. The blockchain technology can satisfy these requirements, ensuring data integrity, univocity, and immutability of the data shared and saved in distributed IoT/IoW systems. In this paper, a deep analysis of requirements for Blockchain based IoT/WoT frameworks has been conducted. The main contributions include (i) formal implications of certifying integrity for data models and for the usage/certification of corresponding instances of entities/ devices and their time series messages in a platform that may present both non-certified and certified models, entities and data messages; (ii) automation of certification and verification processes, which implies mechanisms and formal rules; (iii) flexible certification of data messages enforcing efficiency and sustainability; (iv) support for multi-organization distributed solutions; (v) performance assessment. The solution has been validated with the interconnection to a private/permissioned blockchain developed using

Hyperledger Fabric, while enforcing the solution on Snap4City federated network of platforms for applications in the domain of mobility. The research has been performed in the context of CN MOST, which is the national center on Sustainable Mobility in Italy, and within its flagship action OPTIFaaS.

Keywords: Internet of things; Web of things; Certification of data models; Blockchain; Scalable architecture; Data certification; Time series

Umang Kumar Agrawal, Nibedan Panda, B V Ramana, Debabrata Singh, A K Dalai,
DiagPCNN: Enhancing CNN through Pretrained Model for Brain Tumor Diagnosis,
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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2025.04.496>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S187705092501600X>)

Abstract: Analysis of medical images plays a vital role in the early detection and prognosis of diseases. Among various medical imaging, Magnetic Resonance Imaging(MRI) is valuable in providing insights into the brain artefact. Early classification of brain tumors has become indispensable for doctors and medical persons. With the recent advancements in deep learning, Convolution Neural Networks have gained widespread in the domain of disease diagnosis and medical imaging, due to their notable efficacy and high performance. In this study, we have proposed the DiagPCNN model which incorporates a pre-trained model with CNN for an increment in optimal efficacy of the manifest model. We have also analysed the pros and cons of the DiagPCNN model over eighteen different architectures and three DiagPCNN models outperforms the rest of models with superior accuracy of 96.63, 97.28 and 97.79% respectively. Hence, simplifying their skilfulness in detecting brain tumors to induce the manifest model of a productive and virtuous approach for enhanced prognosis.

Keywords: Deep Learning; CNN; DiagPCNN; Brain MRI; Medical Imaging

Nilantha Prasad, Abebe Diro, Matthew Warren, Mahesh Fernando,

A survey of cyber threat attribution: Challenges, techniques, and future directions,

Computers & Security,

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(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0167404825002950>)

Abstract: The escalating sophistication of cyberattacks, exemplified by supply chain compromises, AI-driven obfuscation, and politically motivated campaigns, makes accurate attribution a critical yet elusive challenge for national security and economic stability. The inability to reliably trace attacks to their source undermines deterrence, distorts policy responses, and erodes trust in digital ecosystems. Traditional methods struggle with the sheer volume of digital evidence, rapidly evolving adversary tactics, and the inherent complexities of cross-border operations. Moreover, existing literature often provides fragmented analyses, focuses narrowly on cyber threat intelligence sharing or specific threat types, or predates significant advancements in AI/ML tailored for attribution. This survey offers a comprehensive, interdisciplinary review of cyber threat attribution, bridging these critical gaps by systematically analyzing its multifaceted dimensions: technical, legal, geopolitical, social, and economic. Employing a rigorous, PRISMA-ScR compliant methodology that included structured screening and quality assessment across six major databases, we critically appraise current techniques and identify a paradigm shift toward data-driven, intelligent approaches. A key contribution is our novel taxonomy, which structures attribution research by attribution confidence & granularity (the Level of attribution), analytical domains (the “How” and “Where” of evidence processing) and adversarial motivation & profile (the “Why” and “Who”), providing a crucial framework for systematic cross-study comparisons in a complex field. Our findings underscore the transformative potential of emerging AI/ML techniques, particularly graph neural networks, in automating analysis, identifying subtle patterns, and extracting crucial insights from vast datasets, thereby revolutionizing attribution accuracy. This research provides actionable insights for practitioners and policymakers, offering a comprehensive roadmap to advance cyber defense and foster a more resilient and secure global digital ecosystem.

Keywords: Cyber threats; Cyber security; Threat attribution; Machine learning; Artificial intelligence

Noptanit Chotisarn, Sarun Gulyanon, Tianye Zhang, Wei Chen,

VISHIEN-MAAT: Scrollytelling visualization design for explaining Siamese Neural Network concept to non-technical users,

Visual Informatics,

Volume 7, Issue 1,

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(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2468502X23000049>)

Abstract: The past decade has witnessed rapid progress in AI research since the breakthrough in deep learning. AI technology has been applied in almost every field; therefore, technical and non-technical end-users must understand these technologies to exploit them. However existing materials are designed for experts, but non-technical users need appealing materials that deliver complex ideas in easy-to-follow steps. One notable tool that fits such a profile is scrollytelling, an approach to storytelling that provides readers with a natural and rich experience at the reader's pace, along with in-depth interactive explanations of complex concepts. Hence, this work proposes a novel visualization design for creating a scrollytelling that can effectively explain an AI concept to non-technical users. As a demonstration of our design, we created a scrollytelling to explain the Siamese Neural Network for the visual similarity matching problem. Our approach helps create a visualization valuable for a short-timeline situation like a sales pitch. The results show that the visualization based on our novel design helps improve non-technical users' perception and machine learning concept knowledge acquisition compared to traditional materials like online articles.

Keywords: Story synthesis; Scrollytelling; Visual storytelling; Visualizing deep learning; Learning science

Naif Almusallam, Junaid Qayyum,

A Hybrid Feature Selection and Clustering-Based Ensemble Learning Approach for Real-Time Fraud Detection in Financial Transactions,

Computers, Materials and Continua,

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<https://doi.org/10.32604/cmc.2025.067220>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1546221825008835>)

Abstract: This paper proposes a novel hybrid fraud detection framework that integrates multi-stage feature selection, unsupervised clustering, and ensemble learning to improve classification performance in financial transaction monitoring systems. The framework is structured into three core layers: (1) feature selection using Recursive Feature Elimination (RFE), Principal Component Analysis (PCA), and Mutual Information (MI) to reduce dimensionality and enhance input relevance; (2) anomaly detection through unsupervised clustering using K-Means, Density-Based Spatial Clustering (DBSCAN), and Hierarchical Clustering to flag suspicious patterns in unlabeled data; and (3) final classification using a voting-based hybrid ensemble of Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest (RF), and Gradient Boosting Classifier (GBC). The experimental evaluation is conducted on a synthetically generated dataset comprising one million financial transactions, with 5% labelled as fraudulent, simulating realistic fraud rates and behavioural features, including transaction time, origin, amount, and geo-location. The proposed model demonstrated a significant improvement over baseline classifiers, achieving an accuracy of 99%, a precision of 99%, a recall of 97%, and an F1-score of 99%. Compared to individual models, it yielded a 9% gain in overall detection accuracy. It reduced the false positive rate to below 3.5%, thereby minimising the operational costs associated with manually reviewing false alerts. The model's interpretability is enhanced by the integration of Shapley Additive Explanations (SHAP) values for feature importance, supporting transparency and regulatory auditability. These results affirm the practical relevance of the proposed system for deployment in real-time fraud detection scenarios such as credit card transactions, mobile banking, and cross-border payments. The study also highlights future directions, including the deployment of lightweight models and the integration of multimodal data for scalable fraud analytics.

Keywords: Fraud detection; financial transactions; economic impact; feature selection; clustering; ensemble learning

Ramanpreet Kaur, Dušan Gabrijelčič, Tomaž Klobučar,

Artificial intelligence for cybersecurity: Literature review and future research directions,

Information Fusion,

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Abstract: Artificial intelligence (AI) is a powerful technology that helps cybersecurity teams automate repetitive tasks, accelerate threat detection and response, and improve the accuracy of their actions to strengthen the security posture against various security issues and cyberattacks. This article presents a systematic literature review and a detailed analysis of AI use cases for cybersecurity provisioning. The review resulted in 2395 studies, of which 236 were identified as primary. This article classifies the identified AI use cases based on a NIST cybersecurity framework using a thematic analysis approach. This classification framework will provide readers with a comprehensive overview of the potential of AI to improve cybersecurity in different contexts. The review also identifies future research opportunities in emerging cybersecurity application areas, advanced AI methods, data representation, and the development of new infrastructures for the successful adoption of AI-based cybersecurity in today's era of digital transformation and polycrisis.

Keywords: Detection; Protection; Response; Recovery; Identify; Learning; Cyberattacks; Taxonomy

Shizhen Bai, Songlin Shi, Chunjia Han, Mu Yang, Brij B. Gupta, Varsha Arya,

Prioritizing user requirements for digital products using explainable artificial intelligence: A data-driven analysis on video conferencing apps,

Future Generation Computer Systems,

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Pages 167-182,
ISSN 0167-739X,
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.future.2024.04.037>.
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Abstract: The advent of Industry 5.0 has brought a wealth of digital information to mobile app stores. With the help of emerging technologies such as machine learning and explainable artificial intelligence (XAI), these large amounts of user-generated data can be efficiently captured and analyzed. In this study, we propose an app store analysis framework and demonstrate the utility of the framework by mining and prioritizing user requirements in three popular video conferencing apps. We used the Sentistrength sentiment analysis tool, structural topic modeling, the Gephi web analysis tool, machine learning, and XAI techniques to conduct an in-depth analysis of user requirements in Microsoft Teams, ZOOM Cloud Meetings, and Google Meet. The findings indicated that Steal data, Audio and video quality, Customer service, Hacker issues, Meeting and account passwords, Mute and unmute, Features, and Office platform were the web conferencing system's key areas for improvement. The study demonstrated the usability of app store analysis frameworks and the great potential of XAI to provide insights about requirements prioritization by interpreting machine learning models. Additionally, it offered valuable suggestions for app developers on using the massive data in app stores to improve their apps.

Keywords: User requirements; Requirements prioritization; Video conferencing apps; App reviews; Text analysis; Explainable artificial intelligence

Qianwen Ariel Xu, Chrisina Jayne, Victor Chang,
An emoji feature-incorporated multi-view deep learning for explainable sentiment classification of social media reviews,
Technological Forecasting and Social Change,
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ISSN 0040-1625,
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(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0040162524001227>)

Abstract: Sentiment analysis has demonstrated its value in a range of high-stakes domains. From financial markets to supply chain management, logistics, and technology legitimacy assessment, sentiment analysis offers insights into public sentiment, actionable data, and improved decision forecasting. This study contributes to this growing body of research by offering a novel multi-view deep learning approach to sentiment analysis that incorporates non-textual features like emojis. The proposed approach considers both textual and emoji views as distinct views of emotional information for the sentiment classification model, and the results acknowledge their individual and combined contributions to sentiment analysis. Comparative analysis with baseline classifiers reveals that incorporating emoji features significantly enriches sentiment analysis, enhancing the accuracy, F1-score, and execution time of the proposed model. Additionally, this study employs LIME for explainable sentiment analysis to provide insights into the model's decision-making process, enabling high-stakes businesses to understand the factors driving customer sentiment. The present study contributes to the literature on multi-view text classification in the context of social media and provides an innovative analytics method for businesses to extract valuable emotional information from electronic word of mouth (eWOM), which can help them stay ahead of the competition in a rapidly evolving digital landscape. In addition, the findings of this paper have important implications for policy development in digital communication and social media monitoring. Recognizing the importance of emojis in sentiment expression can inform policies by helping them better understand public sentiment and tailor policy solutions that better address the concerns of the public.

Keywords: Explainable sentiment analysis; Multi-view learning; High-stakes decision forecasting; Marketing analytics; Social media reviews

Maya Thapa, Ravreet Kaur,
An Explainable Deep – Learning based Multi-Label Image Classification for Chest X-Rays,
Procedia Computer Science,
Volume 258,
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Pages 2425-2434,
ISSN 1877-0509,
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2025.04.505>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877050925016096>)

Abstract: Accurate diagnosis of respiratory diseases from chest X-rays, especially when multiple diseases coexist, is challenging. While deep learning has been effective in multi-label classification, its lack of interpretability hinders its adoption in critical medical applications. We propose an explainable strategy utilizing three distinct techniques-Grad-CAM, LIME, and DeepLIFT—to offer comprehensive discernment into the model's decision-making process. Our two-step training approach involved treating uncertain labels as zeros to establish baseline weights and then retraining with uncertain labels as ones led to significant performance gains, achieving an average AUC of 0.87 on the CheXpert dataset, surpassing existing methods (0.78-0.83). Our findings emphasize the need for comprehensive label analysis in medical imaging and demonstrate the effectiveness of specific explainability techniques in enhancing model interpretability for chest X-ray classification, ultimately aiding radiologists in clinical decision-making.

Keywords: Explainable deep learning; multi-label image classification; chest X-ray; convolutional neural network; transfer learning; Grad-CAM; LIME; DeepLift

Rahul Dwivedi, Sridhar Nerur, Venugopal Balijepally,
Exploring artificial intelligence and big data scholarship in information systems: A citation, bibliographic coupling, and co-word analysis,
International Journal of Information Management Data Insights,
Volume 3, Issue 2,
2023,
100185,
ISSN 2667-0968,
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijime.2023.100185>.
(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2667096823000320>)

Abstract: This research explores extant research on artificial intelligence (AI) and big data published in the premier Information Systems (IS) journals over a period of 26 years (1997–2022), and it uses the techniques of citation analysis, bibliographic coupling, and co-word analysis. Citation analysis results reveal IS as the most cited reference discipline, followed by general business, organization science, and marketing. Two major topical clusters have been identified — problem domain-specific AI (e.g., predictive analytics, machine learning algorithms, and text mining) and organizational-specific AI (e.g., big data capabilities, firm performance, agility, and strategy). Co-word analysis revealed a gradual shift of scholarly interest from problem-domain-specific AI toward organizational-specific AI. Using the citation data, the most influential (cited) authors, (cited) articles, journals, institutions, and countries are identified. Gaps in extant research and future research paths are discussed.

Keywords: Information systems; Artificial intelligence; Big data research; Intellectual structure; Identifying reference disciplines; Citation analysis; Bibliographic coupling; Co-word analysis; Performance analysis

Dennis Herhausen, Stephan Ludwig, Ehsan Abedin, Nasim Ul Haque, David de Jong,
From words to insights: Text analysis in business research,
Journal of Business Research,
Volume 198,
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115491,
ISSN 0148-2963,
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2025.115491>.
(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0148296325003145>)

Abstract: Business success relies on effective stakeholder communication, much of which occurs via or can be transcribed into text. Yet, business researchers often lack coherent frameworks to conceptualize business-relevant communication and its underlying logics. We thus consider business research from a message design logic lens to offer a conceptual foundation for research seeking to understand the content, style, and structure of business communication. Business researchers also underutilize modern tools for analyzing text data. Hence, our comparison of current methodologies for analyzing text (i.e., topic models, dictionaries, supervised machine learning, and large language models) points out their respective advantages, limitations, and applications. An overview of recent studies in the Journal of Business Research identifies how these methods are used to extract insights from business communication. We offer practical guidelines for authors and reviewers on method selection, implementation, and evaluation, and conclude by proposing future directions for business research using text data.

Keywords: Automated text analysis; Business communication; Message design logic

Abdelrahim Ahmad, Peizheng Li, Robert Piechocki, Rui Inacio,
Anomaly detection in offshore open radio access network using long short-term memory models on a novel artificial intelligence-driven cloud-native data platform,
Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence,
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112274,
ISSN 0952-1976,
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(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0952197625022821>)

Abstract: The Radio Access Network (RAN) is a critical component of modern telecommunications infrastructure, currently evolving towards disaggregated and open architectures. These advancements are pivotal for integrating intelligent, data-driven applications aimed at enhancing network reliability and operational autonomy through the introduction of cognitive capabilities, as exemplified by the emerging Open Radio Access Network (O-RAN) standards. Despite its potential, the nascent nature of O-RAN technology presents challenges, primarily due to the absence of mature operational standards. This complicates the management of data and intelligent applications, particularly when integrating with traditional network management and operational support systems. Divergent vendor-specific design approaches further hinder migration and limit solution reusability. These challenges are compounded by a skills gap in telecommunications business-oriented engineering, which remains a key barrier to effective O-RAN deployment and intelligent application development. To address these challenges, Boldyn Networks developed a novel cloud-native data analytics platform, specifically designed to support scalable Artificial Intelligence (AI) integration within O-RAN deployments. This platform underwent rigorous testing in real-world scenarios, and applied advanced AI techniques to improve operational efficiency and customer experience. Implementation involved adopting Development Operations (DevOps) practices, leveraging data lakehouse architectures tailored for AI applications, and employing sophisticated data engineering strategies. The platform successfully addresses

connectivity challenges inherent in real-world offshore wind farm deployments using Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) models for anomaly detection in network connectivity. After integrating the LSTM models into the network control, more than 90 percent of connectivity issues were reduced in runtime. This marks a step toward autonomous, self-organizing, and self-healing networks.

Keywords: Open radio access network; Anomaly detection; Long short-term memory models; Artificial intelligence; Big data platform; Telecommunications; Machine learning operations; Data engineering; Development operations; Cloud-native private networks

Nour Lakhali, Adel Aazami, Sebastian Kummer,

The role of artificial intelligence across the source-to-pay framework: Theoretical and practical aspects,

Digital Business,

Volume 5, Issue 2,

2025,

100160,

ISSN 2666-9544,

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.digbus.2025.100160>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2666954425000559>)

Abstract: The procurement function is undergoing a significant transformation driven by the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and other Industry 4.0 technologies across the Source-to-Pay (S2P) process. While prior research has acknowledged the potential of digital procurement tools, there remains a lack of clarity regarding AI's role in specific stages of the S2P framework. This study addresses that gap by examining how AI is applied across three key procurement domains: Source-to-Contract (S2C), Purchase-to-Pay (P2P), and Supplier Relationship Management (SRM). Using a qualitative approach, we conducted semi-structured interviews with procurement professionals to explore AI's practical uses, perceived benefits, and challenges. The findings show that AI enhances efficiency, decision-making, and supplier collaboration, while also driving cross-cutting advances such as orchestration, Application Programming Interface (API) integration, data governance, and new skill requirements. Beyond these process-level benefits, the study highlights practical implications for organizations, including improved cost control, agility, and stronger supplier relationships. Overall, the research contributes to the literature on AI in supply chain management and offers actionable guidance for organizations seeking to leverage digital transformation to innovate and build resilience in procurement.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence; Industry 4.0 technologies; Procurement; Source-to-pay; Supplier relationship management

Brid Murphy, Orla Feeney, Pierangelo Rosati, Theo Lynn,

Exploring accounting and AI using topic modelling,

International Journal of Accounting Information Systems,

Volume 55,

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100709,

ISSN 1467-0895,

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.accinf.2024.100709>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1467089524000423>)

Abstract: Historically, literature suggests that a variety of accounting roles will be replaced by Artificial Intelligence (AI) and related technologies; however, in recent years there is a growing recognition that accounting can in fact harness AI's potential to add value to organisations. Commentators have highlighted the need for increased research exploring accounting and AI and for accounting scholars to consider multi-disciplinary research in this area. This study uses a form of topic modelling to analyse literature exploring AI and related techniques in an accounting context. Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) has been used to enable probabilistic, machine-based interrogation of large volumes of literature. This study applies LDA to the abstracts of 930 peer-reviewed academic publications from a variety of disciplines to identify the most significant accounting and AI topics discussed in the literature during the period 1990 to 2023. Our findings suggest that prior literature reviews based on more traditional methodologies do not capture a comprehensive picture of accounting and AI research. Eleven topic clusters are identified which provide a comprehensive topology of the extant literature discussing accounting and AI and set out an agenda for future research designed to foster academic progress in the area. It also represents one of the first applications of probabilistic topic modelling to accounting literature.

Keywords: Accounting; Accountant; Artificial intelligence; Topic modelling; Latent Dirichlet Allocation

Svenja M. Hübler, Christian Ertel, Ansgar Heidemann,

Exploring the individual adoption of human resource analytics: Behavioural beliefs and the role of machine learning characteristics,

Technological Forecasting and Social Change,

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123709,

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2024.123709>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0040162524005079>)

Abstract: The technological capabilities of Human Resource Analytics (HRA), enhanced by recent innovations in Machine Learning (ML), offer exciting opportunities. However, organisations often fail to realise these potentials because of a limited understanding of why individuals choose to adopt or disregard respective tools. Prior research on innovation adoption offers preliminary insights but fails to aggregate the determinants of individual adoption into actionable suggestions for decisions in the ML adoption process. Our study applies focused interviews to examine non-ML experts' reasoning for using a specific tool tailored to a public sector organisation, which corresponds to the usual end-user perspective of ML-based HRA adoption. By drawing from the HRA adoption framework, provided by Vargas et al. (2018), we contribute to the literature by identifying relevant beliefs and experiences influencing one's intention to adopt ML-based HRA and by qualitatively linking these beliefs to ML characteristics such as transparency, automation and fairness. For practitioners, we provide actionable guidance emphasising the need to ensure fairness proactively, as interviewees do not consider this aspect when deciding to adopt ML-based HRA.

Keywords: Human resource analytics; Machine learning adoption; Explainable artificial intelligence; Theory of planned behaviour; Employee turnover prediction

Victor Chang, Le Minh Thao Doan, Qianwen Ariel Xu, Karl Hall, Yuanyuan Anna Wang, Muhammad Mustafa Kamal,

Digitalization in omnichannel healthcare supply chain businesses: The role of smart wearable devices,

Journal of Business Research,

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113369,

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2022.113369>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0148296322008347>)

Abstract: The advancement in technology has fostered the prevalence of the Internet of Things (IoT), which enhances healthcare business quality, offers a seamless customer experience, and maximizes turnovers and profits. Consequently, omnichannel services have emerged by integrating online and offline channels and providing customers with more real-time information and services to increase their engagement. Healthcare wearable devices appear as a salient tool to connect healthcare providers and patients and thus become an essential part of the omnichannel environment. Along with this trend, the ethical concerns while using these devices have increasingly intensified and are significant barriers to market expansion. Nevertheless, there is a lack of studies discussing the role of wearables in omnichannel hospital supply chain management and examining the influence of those above concerns on healthcare wearables adoption. Therefore, this study explores these gaps through an integrated approach. Furthermore, we proposed a framework integrating the traditional statistical and machine learning-based approach to analyze a large amount of data; and thereby facilitate a data-driven analytic model to manage omnichannel healthcare supply chain businesses.

Keywords: Wearable devices; Healthcare; Ethical issues; Privacy; Security

Ugochukwu Orji, Elochukwu Ukwandu,

Machine learning for an explainable cost prediction of medical insurance,

Machine Learning with Applications,

Volume 15,

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100516,

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mlwa.2023.100516>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2666827023000695>)

Abstract: Predictive modeling in healthcare continues to be an active actuarial research topic as more insurance companies aim to maximize the potential of Machine Learning (ML) approaches to increase their productivity and efficiency. In this paper, the authors deployed three regression-based ensemble ML models that combine variations of decision trees through Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost), Gradient-boosting Machine (GBM), and Random Forest (RF) methods in predicting medical insurance costs. Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) methods SHapley Additive exPlanations (SHAP) and Individual Conditional Expectation (ICE) plots were deployed to discover and explain the key determinant factors that influence medical insurance premium prices in the dataset. The dataset used comprised 986 records and is publicly available in the KAGGLE repository. The models were evaluated using four performance evaluation metrics, including R-squared (R²), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), and Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE). The results show that all models produced impressive outcomes; however, the XGBoost model achieved a better overall performance although it also expanded more computational resources, while the RF model recorded a lesser prediction error and consumed far fewer computing resources than the XGBoost model. Furthermore, we compared the outcome of both XAI methods in identifying the key determinant features that influenced the PremiumPrices for each model and whereas both XAI methods produced similar outcomes, we found that the ICE plots showed in more detail the interactions between each variable than the SHAP analysis which seemed to be more high-level. It is the aim of the authors that the contributions of this study will help policymakers, insurers, and potential medical insurance buyers in their decision-making process for selecting the right policies that meet their specific needs.

Keywords: Explainable artificial intelligence (XAI); Ensemble machine learning; Medical insurance Costs prediction; Actuarial modeling

Oussama Benbrahim Ansari, Franz-Michael Binninger,

A deep learning approach for estimation of price determinants,

International Journal of Information Management Data Insights,

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ISSN 2667-0968,
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jjime.2022.100101>.
(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2667096822000441>)

Abstract: This paper aims to investigate the spatial price dispersion and estimate the price determinants of a homogeneous product sold by marketing channels in the industrial automation market in the south of Germany. Empirical studies reveal that different prices are charged for the same homogeneous products, which shows a clear deviation from the law of one price. Understanding the key determinants of the prices charged by the marketing channels enables manufacturers to design appropriate channel selection criteria with regional differentiation and to improve their existing channel performance management. This research proposes a new geomarketing approach that combines spatial and hedonic price modeling by using deep learning. Since ANN models are often perceived as a “black box”, this paper demonstrates a technique for extracting knowledge from an ANN to leverage the market intelligence. This study reveals the causal relationships between the explanatory variables and the price within the ANN model. The results indicate that deep learning models provide higher accuracy in modeling the price and its determinants compared to statistical models. However, the econometric model GWR enables detecting the geographical variation, also called spatial heterogeneity, among the retained variables to explain the patterns of price, especially their volatility across space.

Keywords: Artificial neural networks; Deep learning; Geomarketing; Multilayer Perceptron; Price dispersion; Spatial analysis

Malka N. Halgamuge, Dusit Niyato,
Adaptive edge security framework for dynamic IoT security policies in diverse environments,
Computers & Security,
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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cose.2024.104128>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0167404824004334>)

Abstract: The rapid expansion of Internet of Things (IoT) technologies has introduced significant cybersecurity challenges, particularly at the network edge where IoT devices operate. Traditional security policies designed for static environments fall short of addressing the dynamic, heterogeneous, and resource-constrained nature of IoT ecosystems. Existing dynamic security policy models lack versatility and fail to fully integrate comprehensive risk assessments, regulatory compliance, and AI/ML (artificial intelligence/machine learning)-driven adaptability. We develop a novel adaptive edge security framework that dynamically generates and adjusts security policies for IoT edge devices. Our framework integrates a dynamic security policy generator, a conflict detection and resolution in policy generator, a bias-aware risk assessment system, a regulatory compliance analysis system, and an AI-driven adaptability integration system. This approach produces tailored security policies that adapt to changes in the threat landscape, regulatory requirements, and device statuses. Our study identifies critical security challenges in diverse IoT environments and demonstrates the effectiveness of our framework through simulations and real-world scenarios. We found that our framework significantly enhances the adaptability and resilience of IoT security policies. Our results demonstrate the potential of AI/ML integration in creating responsive and robust security measures for IoT ecosystems. The implications of our findings suggest that dynamic and adaptive security frameworks are essential for protecting IoT devices against evolving cyber threats, ensuring compliance with regulatory standards, and maintaining the integrity and availability of IoT services across various applications.

Keywords: Cybersecurity; Edge security; IoT security; Regulatory and compliance; Policy

Katura Gania Khushubu, Abdullah Al Masum, Md Habibur Rahman, Shakh Md Shakib Hasan, Md Imranul Hoque Bhuiyan, Mohammad Rasel Mahmud, S.M. Masfequier Rahman Swapno, Abhishek Appaji,
TransUNetB: An advanced Transformer–UNet framework for efficient and explainable brain tumor segmentation,
Informatics in Medicine Unlocked,
Volume 59,
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(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2352914825000954>)

Abstract: This study presents TransUNetB, a hybrid architecture that combines Transformer and UNet for multi-class brain tumor segmentation. This model integrates global context modeling with precise spatial localization. A lightweight Transformer encoder at the bottleneck captures long-range dependencies, while the U-Net's skip pathways preserve fine anatomical details. Additionally, a multi-scale decoder fusion module consolidates features at various resolutions, enhancing the clarity of tumor boundaries in heterogeneous, low-contrast conditions. Our contributions are threefold: (1) a simple, efficient design that integrates bottleneck self-attention with multi-scale fusion for robust ED/TC/ET segmentation; (2) a comprehensive ablation of design choices—attention type, positional encoding, fusion strategy, loss formulation, and patch size—quantifying their impact on accuracy and efficiency; and (3) an explainability analysis using Grad-CAM with quantitative focus/entropy measures to verify that salient regions align with clinical tumor substructures. Evaluated on the BraTS 2020 and BraTS 2021 datasets, TransUNetB achieves a Dice score of 98.90 % and an Intersection over Union (IoU) score of 96.10 %. It outperforms strong CNN and vision-transformer baselines while maintaining a competitive runtime of approximately 63 ms per image. These results suggest that combining global attention with spatially faithful decoding provides a favorable trade-off

between accuracy and efficiency for clinical deployment. We also discuss the generalization of our model beyond MRI cohorts, practical constraints in resource-limited settings, and future research avenues, including attention-guided fusion and broader multi-center validation.

Keywords: Healthcare; Tumor segmentation; Deep learning; Transformer; UNet; Medical imaging; XAI

Olof Björnelid, Welf Löwe,

Real-world validation of a framework for automated knowledge driven feature engineering inspired by medical domain experts,

Informatics in Medicine Unlocked,

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101532,

ISSN 2352-9148,

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.imu.2024.101532>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2352914824000881>)

Abstract: Knowledge discovery from real-world data in health care can be demanding due to unstructured data and low registration quality in electronic health records (EHRs). This requires close collaboration of domain experts and data scientists. To perform the knowledge discovery process more effectively and efficiently, a framework for automatic Knowledge Driven Feature Engineering (aKDFE) has been developed. Central to aKDFE is an automated feature engineering (FE), i.e., an automated construction of new, highly informative variables, referred to as features, from those directly observed and recorded, e.g., in EHRs. The framework learns and aggregates domain knowledge to generate features that are more informative compared to those recorded in EHRs or manually engineered (manual FE) as done in medical research projects today. Manual KDFE is a systematic manual FE process, which improves prediction performance without loss of explainability of the predictions. But the following research questions remained open: (i) is it possible to automate KDFE, (ii) are aKDFE features more informative than features from a manual FE process, and (iii) does aKDFE produce explainable and transparent results? To summarize the present study, aKDFE is (i) more efficient than manual FE since it automates the manual knowledge discovery and FE processes. It is (ii) more effective due to its higher predictive power compared to manual KDFE. This was evaluated on a real-world medical research project by comparing the classification ability when using manual and aKDFE features in machine learning (ML) models, measured as the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUROC). The project included 26,992 patients regarding “Negative bone structure effects of antiepileptic drug consumption”. The baseline features (manual FE) used in studied project were compared with features generated by aKDFE; aKDFE-generated features resulted in higher AUROC than baseline features, with a p-value <0.05. Finally, aKDFE (iii) applies and describes data pivoting and feature generation as explicit and transparent operation sequences on EHR features. Inefficiency issues remain, mainly regarding non-automatic FE and baseline generation. Threat of validity to the aKDFE framework exists in the selection of the pivoting method, the generalization of used FE operations and rules, and usage of evaluation metrics.

Keywords: Feature engineering (FE); Medical registry research; Automated knowledge discovery in databases (KDD); Electronic health record (EHR); Medical domain knowledge; Iterative FE

Thaer Thaher, Muhammed Saffarini, Majdi Mafarja, Abdulaziz Alashbi, Abdul Hakim Mohamed, Ayman A. El-Saleh,

A Hybrid Approach for Heavily Occluded Face Detection Using Histogram of Oriented Gradients and Deep Learning Models,

CMES - Computer Modeling in Engineering and Sciences,

Volume 144, Issue 2,

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(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1526149225002516>)

Abstract: Face detection is a critical component in modern security, surveillance, and human-computer interaction systems, with widespread applications in smartphones, biometric access control, and public monitoring. However, detecting faces with high levels of occlusion, such as those covered by masks, veils, or scarves, remains a significant challenge, as traditional models often fail to generalize under such conditions. This paper presents a hybrid approach that combines traditional handcrafted feature extraction technique called Histogram of Oriented Gradients (HOG) and Canny edge detection with modern deep learning models. The goal is to improve face detection accuracy under occlusions. The proposed method leverages the structural strengths of HOG and edge-based object proposals while exploiting the feature extraction capabilities of Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). The effectiveness of the proposed model is assessed using a custom dataset containing 10,000 heavily occluded face images and a subset of the Common Objects in Context (COCO) dataset for non-face samples. The COCO dataset was selected for its variety and realism in background contexts. Experimental evaluations demonstrate significant performance improvements compared to baseline CNN models. Results indicate that DenseNet121 combined with HOG outperforms other counterparts in classification metrics with an F1-score of 87.96% and precision of 88.02%. Enhanced performance is achieved through reduced false positives and improved localization accuracy with the integration of object proposals based on Canny and contour detection. While the proposed method increases inference time from 33.52 to 97.80 ms, it achieves a notable improvement in precision from 80.85% to 88.02% when comparing the baseline DenseNet121 model to its hybrid counterpart. Limitations of the method include higher computational cost and the need for careful tuning of parameters across the edge detection, handcrafted features, and CNN components. These findings highlight the potential of combining handcrafted and learned features for occluded face detection tasks.

Keywords: Occluded face detection; HOG; canny edge detection; deep learning; features extraction

David Sjödin, Vinit Parida, Marko Kohtamäki,

Artificial intelligence enabling circular business model innovation in digital servitization: Conceptualizing dynamic capabilities, AI capacities, business models and effects, *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, Volume 197, 2023, 122903, ISSN 0040-1625, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2023.122903>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0040162523005887>)

Abstract: This study explores the potential of AI to enable circular business model innovation (CBMI) for industrial manufacturers and the corresponding AI capacities and dynamic capabilities required for their commercialization. Employing an analysis of six leading B2B firms engaged in digital servitization, we conceptualize the perceptive, predictive, and prescriptive capacities of AI, which enhance resource efficiency by automating and augmenting data-driven analysis and decision making. We further identify two innovative classes of AI-enabled CBMs – augmentation (e.g., optimization solutions) and automation (e.g., autonomous solutions) business models – and their main circular value drivers. Finally, our research reveals novel dynamic capabilities underpinning the innovation of AI-enabled business models – value discovery, value realization, and value optimization capabilities – which enable manufacturers to make economic and sustainable values come to life in collaborating with customers and ecosystem partners. This study represents an important step in our understanding of how AI can drive circularity and sustainable innovation in industrial digital servitization. Overall, our study contributes to practice and the academic literature on AI, circular business models, and digital servitization by highlighting the potential of AI to empower CBMs for industrial manufacturers and the underlying processes of this digital transformation.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence; Digital transformation; Circular business models; Digital servitization; Sustainability; Circular economy; Ecosystem; Twin transition; Platform

Khadija Khamis Alnofeli, Shahriar Akter, Venkata Yanamandram, *Unlocking the power of AI in CRM: A comprehensive multidimensional exploration*, *Journal of Innovation & Knowledge*, Volume 10, Issue 3, 2025, 100731, ISSN 2444-569X, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jik.2025.100731>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2444569X25000769>)

Abstract: Artificial intelligence (AI) is revolutionising customer relationship management (CRM) across various sectors, fundamentally altering strategic business operations. This study examines the capabilities of AI-powered CRM systems, drawing on empirical evidence arising from thematic analyses of 64 scholarly articles and insights gained from 24 in-depth interviews with CRM experts. The research identifies and systematically categorises three major dimensions and eight sub-dimensions of AI-powered CRM capabilities, providing a structured framework that encapsulates the complex interplay that occurs between these elements. These dimensions include data management, multi-channel integration, and tailored service offerings, each underpinning the nuanced integration of AI into CRM practices. Critically, the study integrates these findings within the theoretical framework of the microfoundations of Dynamic Capabilities (DC), enriching the discourse on how AI can strategically enhance CRM systems and offering a nuanced understanding of the factors driving AI adoption within CRM. By mapping these capabilities against the microfoundations of DC theory, the research delineates the strategic implications for organisations striving to leverage AI to enhance their competitive advantage.

Keywords: AI-powered CRM capabilities; Microfoundations of dynamic capabilities; Data management; Multichannel integration; Service offerings

Arthur Matta, Luís Miguel Matos, André Pilastrri, Jorge Miguel Silva, Miguel Bastos Gomes, Paulo Cortez, *Ahead of Time Prediction of Decorated Particleboard Production Disruptions and Defects Using Single and Multi-Target AutoML*, *Procedia Computer Science*, Volume 246, 2024, Pages 2110-2119, ISSN 1877-0509, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2024.09.633>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877050924026875>)

Abstract: This paper proposes a Machine Learning (ML) approach to perform an Ahead-of-Time (AoT) prediction of decorated particle-board production disruptions and defects. We worked with a Portuguese company that is adopting the Industry 4.0 concept aiming to improve their decorated particleboard production planning (e.g., reducing production time and waste of materials). This company's business needs are addressed in terms of two nontrivial binary Classification tasks (production disruptions and defects). The AoT prediction is achieved by using only input attributes available before the execution of the production process. To reduce the modeling effort, we focus on Automated ML (AutoML) methods, under two main approaches: Single-Target Classification (STC) and Multi-Target Classification (MTC). The former is achieved by adopting the popular H2O AutoML tool, while the latter adopts a deep learning neural network automatically tuned by using a Bayesian search. The computational experiments adopted a realistic rolling window evaluation over recently collected industrial data (comprising 14 months). Overall, interesting predictive results were achieved by both AutoML approaches, outperforming a baseline Decision Tree method. In

addition, an eXplainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI) method based on a Sensitivity Analysis (SA) was adopted, allowing the identification of the most relevant inputs, which is valuable knowledge to support the decorated particleboard production planning.

Keywords: Automated Machine learning; Production Planning; Quality Control; Production Uptime; Decorated Particleboard

Tarique Ameer, Omid Fatahi Valilai,
Cloud-native causal AI for supply chain KPI monitoring: A GCP framework to diagnose out-of-stock events,
Machine Learning with Applications,
Volume 22,
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100765,
ISSN 2666-8270,
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mlwa.2025.100765>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2666827025001483>)

Abstract: Effective supply chain management (SCM) is essential for ensuring operational efficiency, cost optimization, and customer satisfaction. In an increasingly dynamic business environment, the integration of cloud computing and Causal Artificial Intelligence (AI) presents new opportunities for value creation and intelligent decision-making. This study proposes a framework that leverages the capabilities of Google® Cloud Platform (GCP) for real-time Key Performance Indicator (KPI) monitoring and supply chain analytics. By incorporating Causal AI, the framework enables the identification of underlying causes of out-of-stock (OOS) situations, rather than merely observing correlations. The research presents an end-to-end architecture combining data pipelines, real-time dashboards, and causal inference models to proactively detect and address OOS risks. This integrated, data-driven approach aims to improve inventory accuracy, enhance forecasting, and ultimately strengthen supply chain resilience and responsiveness.

Keywords: Causal AI; Supply chain analytics; Google® Cloud Platform (GCP); Supply chain value creation; Data-Driven KPI Measurement; Out-of-stock (OOS)

Lomat Haider Chowdhury, Shaira Tabassum, Swakkhar Shatabda, Ashir Ahmed,
An optimized data analytics pipeline for improving healthcare diagnosis using ensemble learning,
Informatics in Medicine Unlocked,
Volume 53,
2025,
101623,
ISSN 2352-9148,
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.imu.2025.101623>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2352914825000115>)

Abstract: Healthcare diagnosis is a process physicians follow before prescribing the patients. The medical doctors may make an early prediction by observing the physical signs and symptoms. Imposing a treatment without proper diagnosis cannot guarantee a cure and sometimes may lead the patient to a more detrimental scenario. However, the cost of healthcare diagnosis makes people indifferent to going through the process. Big data and machine learning are already in use to contribute to the healthcare diagnosis sector with the available data which is enormously growing through the digitalization of the system. Yet the difficulty remains since the raw data contains noise including missing values, outliers, and an imbalanced number of samples. These properties in a dataset make it challenging to implement any diagnosis model. A complete patient profile cannot be generated due to missing values, which may affect the final prediction. Outliers in a medical dataset represent extreme cases and rare conditions, or they may even be generated due to data entry errors. An excessive number of outliers may lead to a skewed and incorrect prediction. An imbalanced dataset makes it challenging to identify the minority classes appropriately and mostly generates a biased model for majority class instances. A combination of advanced preprocessing techniques and reliable model selection are required to address these challenges effectively. This paper proposes a data analytics pipeline on a Portable Health Clinic (PHC) dataset. The paper systematically evaluates different preprocessing methods for missing value imputation, outliers detection, and data balancing and offers a comprehensive preprocessing framework. Later, five state-of-the-art ensemble models for healthcare diagnosis were implemented along with a proposed ensemble machine learning model, KNN-XGBoost-SVM-Random Forest (KNN-X-SVM-R). The proposed model achieved an accuracy of 97.03% which supersedes all the other state-of-the-art models. To reaffirm the rectification of our model, we experimented with it on another COVID-19 routine blood test dataset. In both cases, our proposed model acquired better results regarding different performance measures. Validating the approach on a secondary dataset strengthens the robustness of the proposed methodology. The recommended preprocessing and modeling approach can be adopted to enhance diagnostic systems and improve patient outcomes.

Keywords: Healthcare diagnosis; Data analytics; Noise handling; Portable Health Clinic; COVID-19

Seungkyu Park, Joong yoon Lee, Jooyeoun Lee,
AI system architecture design methodology based on IMO (Input-AI Model-Output) structure for successful AI adoption in organizations,
Data & Knowledge Engineering,
Volume 150,
2024,
102264,
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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.datak.2023.102264>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0169023X23001246>)

Abstract: With the advancement of AI technology, the successful AI adoption in organizations has become a top priority in modern society. However, many organizations still struggle to articulate the necessary AI, and AI experts have difficulties understanding the problems faced by these organizations. This knowledge gap makes it difficult for organizations to identify the technical requirements, such as necessary data and algorithms, for adopting AI. To overcome this problem, we propose a new AI system architecture design methodology based on the IMO (Input-AI Model-Output) structure. The IMO structure enables effective identification of the technical requirements necessary to develop real AI models. While previous research has identified the importance and challenges of technical requirements, such as data and AI algorithms, for AI adoption, there has been little research on methodology to concretize them. Our methodology is composed of three stages: problem definition, system AI solution, and AI technical solution to design the AI technology and requirements that organizations need at a system level. The effectiveness of our methodology is demonstrated through a case study, logical comparative analysis with other studies, and experts reviews, which demonstrate that our methodology can support successful AI adoption to organizations.

Keywords: AI(Artificial intelligence); AI system architecture design; System engineering; Requirements engineering; AI adoption

Ross Maciejewski, Yuxin Ma, Jonas Lukasczyk,

The Visual Analytics and Data Exploration Research Lab at Arizona State University,

Visual Informatics,

Volume 5, Issue 1,

2021,

Pages 14-22,

ISSN 2468-502X,

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.visinf.2020.12.001>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2468502X20300929>)

Abstract: This article describes the research agenda for the Visual Analytics and Data Exploration Research (VADER) Lab at Arizona State University. Over the past decade, the VADER Lab has focused on creating novel algorithms, tools and visualizations for spatiotemporal data. This article will highlight past success in spatiotemporal analysis, explainable AI, graph mining, and mathematical topology. While, at first, these topics seem largely disjoint, we will describe how the underpinnings of spatiotemporal analysis has informed the various research directions in the VADER Lab, and how this research agenda has served to form a network of strong international collaborations. Finally, we will outline a vision for the Lab's future research.

Keywords: Visualization; Spatiotemporal; Explainable AI; Topology

Abebe Diro, Shahriar Kaiser, Athanasios V. Vasilakos, Adnan Anwar, Araz Nasirian, Gaddisa Olani,

Anomaly detection for space information networks: A survey of challenges, techniques, and future directions,

Computers & Security,

Volume 139,

2024,

103705,

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cose.2024.103705>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0167404824000063>)

Abstract: Space anomaly detection plays a critical role in safeguarding the integrity and reliability of space systems amid the rising tide of threats. This survey aims to deepen comprehension of space cyber threats through space threat modeling, and meticulously examine the unique challenges of space anomaly detection. The survey identifies scalability, real-time detection, limited labeled data availability, concept drift, and adversarial attacks as key challenges based on thorough literature analysis and synthesis. By extensively exploring state-of-the-art anomaly detection techniques, the study evaluates their applicability, strengths, and limitations within space networks. Going beyond analysis, a notable contribution of this work involves integrating stream-based and graph-based methods, tailored to capture the intricate temporal and structural relationships inherent in space networks. This innovative hybrid approach holds promise for heightened detection accuracy and sets the stage for future research endeavors. As space threats continue evolving in both number and sophistication, this survey timely provides insights, recommendations, and a clear roadmap for researchers, engineers, and practitioners to fortify space anomaly detection mechanisms.

Keywords: AIndex terms - anomaly detection; Space security; Space anomaly detection; Cybersecurity; Space information networks; Dynamic space anomaly detection

Angel Dacal-Nieto, Juan José Areal, Victor Alonso-Ramos, Marcos Lluch,

Integrating a data analytics system in automotive manufacturing: background, methodology and learned lessons,

Procedia Computer Science,

Volume 200,

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Pages 718-726,

ISSN 1877-0509,

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2022.01.270>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877050922002794>)

Abstract: Integrating and exploiting a data analytics system in manufacturing is a complex task that involves different skills and most of the times requires to handle a brownfield scenario. Under this context, this paper aims to act as a guide to study the background and justification to industrialize a data analytics system in manufacturing, providing a methodology, learned lessons and potential use cases. As application of this methodology, the digitalization case of an automotive manufacturing factory is shown, which includes scenarios dealing with improvement of quality, process optimization and early detection of deviation of parameters. Even in an early stage of implementation, it has been demonstrated that these actions provide an economical advantage for the factory, in terms of productivity improvements and efficiency increasings. This methodology can be useful not only in automotive, but also in other manufacturing domains.

Keywords: automotive; manufacturing; data analytics; digitalization; industry 4.0

Mojtaba Rezaei,

Artificial intelligence in knowledge management: Identifying and addressing the key implementation challenges,

Technological Forecasting and Social Change,

Volume 217,

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124183,

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2025.124183>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0040162525002148>)

Abstract: In today's digital landscape, Knowledge Management (KM) is crucial for organisational competitiveness. Artificial Intelligence (AI) offers transformative potential for KM practices, yet its integration presents multifaceted challenges. This study addresses significant gaps in the literature by identifying and prioritising critical challenges associated with AI integration in KM. Employing a tripartite methodological approach, this research combines a literature review on KM and AI's challenges, a Delphi study with domain experts, and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) across four KM processes. Data from retail sector professionals validate the challenges identified by experts. Findings reveal a comprehensive landscape of challenges, categorised into technological, organisational, and ethical domains, with variations across different KM processes. The study contributes to the field by comprehensively exploring AI-related challenges in KM, offering a quantitative ranking, and enhancing understanding of the AI-KM interplay. This research provides valuable insights for business leaders, facilitating the development of strategies to foster robust knowledge ecosystems. By addressing these challenges proactively, organisations can enhance their KM practices, leveraging AI to maintain competitiveness in an increasingly digital business environment. The study contributes to theoretical discourse and offers practical implications for organisations navigating AI integration in their KM practices.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence (AI); Knowledge management (KM); Knowledge creation (KC); Knowledge storage (KTS); Knowledge sharing (KS); Knowledge application (KA); Delphi method; Technological challenges; Organisational challenges; Ethical challenges; CFA

Elodie Escriva, Tom Lefrere, Manon Martin, Julien Aligon, Alexandre Chanson, Jean-Baptiste Excoffier, Nicolas Labroche, Chantal Soulé-Dupuy, Paul Monsarrat,

Effective data exploration through clustering of local attributive explanations,

Information Systems,

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102464,

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(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0306437924001224>)

Abstract: Machine Learning (ML) has become an essential tool for modeling complex phenomena, offering robust predictions and comprehensive data analysis. Nevertheless, the lack of interpretability in these predictions often results in a closed-box effect, which the field of eXplainable Machine Learning (XML) aims to address. Local attributive XML methods, in particular, provide explanations by quantifying the contribution of each attribute to individual predictions, referred to as influences. This type of explanation is the most acute as it focuses on each instance of the dataset and allows the detection of individual differences. Additionally, aggregating local explanations allows for a deeper analysis of the underlying data. In this context, influences can be considered as a new data space to reveal and understand complex data patterns. We hypothesize that these influences, derived from ML explanations, are more informative than the original raw data, especially for identifying homogeneous groups within the data. To identify such groups effectively, we utilize a clustering approach. We compare clusters formed using raw data against those formed using influences computed by various local attributive XML methods. Our findings reveal that clusters based on influences consistently outperform those based on raw data, even when using models with low accuracy.

Keywords: Explainable machine learning (XML); Prediction explanation; Explanations clustering; Instance clustering; Machine learning explanation; Explainable artificial intelligence (XAI)

Lorenzo Bruno Pratavia, Nathan D'souza, Claire Louise Charlton,

Exploring artificial intelligence for third-party logistics service providers: a dynamic capabilities perspective,

International Journal of Physical Distribution & Logistics Management,

Volume 56, Issue 4,
2025,
Pages 450-484,
ISSN 0960-0035,
<https://doi.org/10.1108/IJPDLM-11-2024-0431>.
(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0960003525000236>)

Abstract:

Purpose Artificial Intelligence (AI) is increasingly considered a transformative force within the logistics industry, improving efficiency and enhancing effectiveness for many organisations, including third-party logistics service providers (3PLs). However, the academic literature reveals a limited understanding of how 3PLs can approach the opportunities offered by AI. To fill this gap, we leverage the dynamic capabilities theory to explore AI adoption within the 3PL industry.

Design/methodology/approach We developed a single case study focusing on a leading British 3PL that introduced AI to improve warehousing operations and planning activities. We collected data through two rounds of qualitative interviews with managerial-level stakeholders from different departments and two on-site visits. Through abductive reasoning, we iteratively compared empirics with the available theoretical knowledge to illuminate how 3PLs can approach AI opportunities through their sensing, seizing and reconfiguring dynamic capabilities.

Findings Findings illustrate several micro-foundations underpinning higher-order dynamic capabilities. Sensing AI opportunities critically depends on building internal AI awareness as well as involving customers to embed their perspectives, leading to prioritising AI use cases. Seizing starts with aligning use cases with the business strategy, then procuring AI solutions and assessing their security and ethical implications before embedding different AI tools. These initiatives foster resource reconfiguration by embracing a cultural shift involving 3PLs and their customers and developing a robust data infrastructure to support AI efforts. Building on these findings, we suggest evolutionary patterns for dynamic capabilities through AI adoption.

Originality/value Existing research has yet to fully explore how 3PLs can approach AI adoption. The study contextualises the dynamic capabilities theory for AI-driven opportunities, elaborating on earlier studies to identify micro-foundations for 3PLs' higher-order dynamic capabilities. It proposes a set of research propositions and offers a research agenda to foster future exploration about embedding AI into logistics operations. By focusing on 3PLs in the context of rising digitalisation, the study highlights how firms can navigate the complexities of AI adoption, offering original insights to leverage the synergies among human workforce, technological tools and physical assets.

Keywords: 3PL; Artificial intelligence; AI; Dynamic capabilities

Rezaul Haque, Mahbub Alam Khan, Hamdadur Rahman, Shakil Khan, Md Ismail Hossain Siddiqui, Zishad Hossain Limon, S M Masfequier Rahman Swapno, Abhishek Appaji,

Explainable deep stacking ensemble model for accurate and transparent brain tumor diagnosis,

Computers in Biology and Medicine,

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110166,

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(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0010482525005177>)

Abstract: Early detection of brain tumors in MRI images is vital for improving treatment results. However, deep learning models face challenges like limited dataset diversity, class imbalance, and insufficient interpretability. Most studies rely on small, single-source datasets and do not combine different feature extraction techniques for better classification. To address these challenges, we propose a robust and explainable stacking ensemble model for multiclass brain tumor classification. To address these challenges, we propose a stacking ensemble model that combines EfficientNetB0, MobileNetV2, GoogleNet, and Multi-level CapsuleNet, using CatBoost as the meta-learner for improved feature aggregation and classification accuracy. This ensemble approach captures complex tumor characteristics while enhancing robustness and interpretability. The proposed model integrates EfficientNetB0, MobileNetV2, GoogleNet, and a Multi-level CapsuleNet within a stacking framework, utilizing CatBoost as the meta-learner to improve feature aggregation and classification accuracy. We created two large MRI datasets by merging data from four sources: BraTS, Msoud, Br35H, and SARTAJ. To tackle class imbalance, we applied Borderline-SMOTE and data augmentation. We also utilized feature extraction methods, along with PCA and Gray Wolf Optimization (GWO). Our model was validated through confidence interval analysis and statistical tests, demonstrating superior performance. Error analysis revealed misclassification trends, and we assessed computational efficiency regarding inference speed and resource usage. The proposed ensemble achieved 97.81% F1 score and 98.75% PR AUC on M1, and 98.32% F1 score with 99.34% PR AUC on M2. Moreover, the model consistently surpassed state-of-the-art CNNs, Vision Transformers, and other ensemble methods in classifying brain tumors across individual four datasets. Finally, we developed a web-based diagnostic tool that enables clinicians to interact with the proposed model and visualize decision-critical regions in MRI scans using Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI). This study connects high-performing AI models with real clinical applications, providing a reliable, scalable, and efficient diagnostic solution for brain tumor classification.

Keywords: Brain tumor; Cancer diagnosis; Visual intelligence; Explainable AI; Diagnostic tool

Byron Graham, Karen Bonner,

The role of institutions in early-stage entrepreneurship: An explainable artificial intelligence approach,

Journal of Business Research,
Volume 175,
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114567,
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(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0148296324000717>)

Abstract: Although the importance of institutional conditions in fostering entrepreneurship is well established, less is known about the dominance of institutional dimensions, their predictive ability, and more complex non-linear relationships. To overcome the limitations of traditional regression approaches in addressing these gaps we apply techniques from explainable artificial intelligence to study the dominance and non-linearity of institutional dimensions in predicting country-level early-stage entrepreneurship. Eight machine learning algorithms are applied to matched data from the Global Entrepreneurship Monitor, Index of Economic Freedom, and World Bank across 573 observations from 81 countries. Findings from the most accurate random forest model reveal considerable non-linearity in the relationships between institutional dimensions and entrepreneurship, as well as heterogeneity in the importance of individual dimensions, with an overall trend towards the dominance of cultural-cognitive institutions. These findings contribute to institutional theory and highlight important areas where machine learning methods can contribute to entrepreneurship research and policy.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship; Explainable artificial intelligence; Institutional theory; Machine learning; Entrepreneurship policy

María Rosalía Vicente, Carla Álvarez-Rodríguez, Ana Suárez-Álvarez,
An old familiar song? Assessing the artificial intelligence divide among the regions of the European Union and its connections with digital divides,
Telecommunications Policy,
Volume 49, Issue 8,
2025,
103030,
ISSN 0308-5961,
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.telpol.2025.103030>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0308596125001272>)

Abstract: This paper explores the use of artificial intelligence (AI) tools by firms across the regions of the European Union. Using the multivariate technique of factor analysis on a set of AI variables, we assess regional levels of AI use and identify both leading and lagging regions. Within countries territorial disparities are also measured. In addition, we explore the extent to which AI use is linked to regional levels of digitalization. Using spatial econometric models, our findings suggest that regional levels of AI use by firms are explained by past usage of digital tools in a region, i.e., by factors related to the second level of the digital divide. No significant relationship is found either for access or outcomes. Furthermore, what neighboring regions do also play a role. Results indicate the existence of complementary effects in AI use between a region and neighbors; meanwhile the relationship would be negative between a region's use of AI and neighbors' digital use.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence (AI); Digital divide; Regions; Spatial modeling; Technological diffusion; European Union (EU)

Sabina-Cristiana Necula, Napoleon-Alexandru Sireteanu,
A Hierarchical Attention Framework for Business Information Systems: Theoretical Foundation and Proof-of-Concept Implementation,
Computers, Materials and Continua,
Volume 86, Issue 2,
2025,
Pages 1-34,
ISSN 1546-2218,
<https://doi.org/10.32604/cmc.2025.070861>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1546221825012160>)

Abstract: Modern business information systems face significant challenges in managing heterogeneous data sources, integrating disparate systems, and providing real-time decision support in complex enterprise environments. Contemporary enterprises typically operate 200+ interconnected systems, with research indicating that 52% of organizations manage three or more enterprise content management systems, creating information silos that reduce operational efficiency by up to 35%. While attention mechanisms have demonstrated remarkable success in natural language processing and computer vision, their systematic application to business information systems remains largely unexplored. This paper presents the theoretical foundation for a Hierarchical Attention-Based Business Information System (HABIS) framework that applies multi-level attention mechanisms to enterprise environments. We provide a comprehensive mathematical formulation of the framework, analyze its computational complexity, and present a proof-of-concept implementation with simulation-based validation that demonstrates a 42% reduction in cross-system query latency compared to legacy ERP modules and 70% improvement in prediction accuracy over baseline methods. The theoretical framework introduces four hierarchical attention levels: system-level attention for dynamic weighting of business systems, process-level attention for business process prioritization, data-level attention for critical information selection, and temporal attention for time-sensitive pattern recognition. Our complexity analysis demonstrates that the framework achieves $O(n \log n)$ computational complexity for attention computation, making it scalable to large enterprise environments including retail supply chains with 200+ system-scale deployments. The proof-of-concept implementation validates the theoretical framework's

feasibility with MSE loss of 0.439 and response times of 0.000120 s per query, demonstrating its potential for addressing key challenges in business information systems. This work establishes a foundation for future empirical research and practical implementation of attention-driven enterprise systems.

Keywords: Attention mechanisms; business information systems; theoretical framework; enterprise architecture; complex systems; hierarchical attention

Heinz Herrmann,

The arcanum of artificial intelligence in enterprise applications: Toward a unified framework,

Journal of Engineering and Technology Management,

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101716,

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jengtecman.2022.101716>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0923474822000467>)

Abstract: Disagreement and confusion about artificial intelligence (AI) terminology impede researchers, innovators, and practitioners when developing and implementing enterprise applications. The prevailing ambiguities and use of buzzwords are exacerbated by media and vendor marketing hype. This study identifies several ambiguities within and across AI fields and subfields. Combining a systematic review with a sequential mixed-models design, a total of 26,143 publications were reviewed and mapped, making this the largest conceptual study in the AI field. A unified framework is proposed as an Euler diagram to bring about clarity through a "common language" for AI researchers, innovators, and practitioners.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence; Unified framework; Systematic review; Science mapping; Systematic science mapping

Juan Sequeda, Dean Allemang, Bryon Jacob,

Knowledge Graphs as a source of trust for LLM-powered enterprise question answering,

Journal of Web Semantics,

Volume 85,

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100858,

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.websem.2024.100858>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1570826824000441>)

Abstract: Generative AI provides an innovative and exciting way to manage knowledge and data at any scale; for small projects, at the enterprise level, and even at a world wide web scale. It is tempting to think that Generative AI has made other knowledge-based technologies obsolete; that anything we wanted to do with knowledge-based systems, Knowledge Graphs or even expert systems can instead be done with Generative AI. Our position is counter to that conclusion. Our practical experience on implementing enterprise question answering systems using Generative AI has shown that Knowledge Graphs support this infrastructure in multiple ways: they provide a formal framework to evaluate the validity of a query generated by an LLM, serve as a foundation for explaining results, and offer access to governed and trusted data. In this position paper, we share our experience, present industry needs, and outline the opportunities for future research contributions.

Keywords: Knowledge Graph; LLM; Large Language Model; Generative AI; Question answering; Knowledge engineering; SPARQL; SQL; OWL; R2RML

Gonzalo Nápoles, Isel Grau, Leonardo Concepción, Lisa Koutsoviti Koumeri, João Paulo Papa,

Modeling implicit bias with fuzzy cognitive maps,

Neurocomputing,

Volume 481,

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Pages 33-45,

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neucom.2022.01.070>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S092523122200090X>)

Abstract: This paper presents a Fuzzy Cognitive Map model to quantify implicit bias in structured datasets where features can be numeric or discrete. In our proposal, problem features are mapped to neural concepts that are initially activated by experts when running what-if simulations, whereas weights connecting the neural concepts represent absolute correlation/association patterns between features. In addition, we introduce a new reasoning mechanism equipped with a normalization-like transfer function that prevents neurons from saturating. Another advantage of this new reasoning mechanism is that it can easily be controlled by regulating nonlinearity when updating neurons' activation values in each iteration. Finally, we study the convergence of our model and derive analytical conditions concerning the existence and unicity of fixed-point attractors.

Keywords: Fairness; Implicit bias; Fuzzy cognitive maps; Convergence analysis

Siji Rani S, Srija Garine, Papolu Hema Janardhana, Lakkireddy Lakshmi Prabhanjan Reddy, Penubothu Jagadeesh Venkata Kumar, Chapa Gagan Dwaz,
Deep Learning-based Cavity Detection in Diverse Intraoral Images: A Web-based Tool for Accessible Dental Care,
Procedia Computer Science,
Volume 233,
2024,
Pages 882-891,
ISSN 1877-0509,
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2024.03.277>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877050924006379>)

Abstract: Dental cavities represent a widespread oral health issue on a global scale, impacting individuals across all age groups. The conventional approach to detecting cavities involves a visual examination by dentists, which is not only time-consuming but also subjective. Current methods for dental cavity detection heavily rely on subjective visual inspections, which may overlook early or concealed cavities. In this research paper, we present CatchCavity, a web application tool that utilizes deep learning for cavity detection in teeth. The diagnostic tool enables users to upload dental images, facilitating the assessment of dental cavity status. Furthermore, the web application functions as an online dental diagnostic service, providing the capability to securely store patients' dental records and information in a dedicated database. The system is trained on a dataset of annotated images and employs a convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture for accurate cavity detection. We evaluate the system's performance using metrics such as accuracy and loss. Our results showcase that the proposed system attains a high level of accuracy and efficiency in detecting dental cavities, achieving an overall accuracy of 98.7%. Additionally, our system surpasses traditional cavity detection methods, highlighting the possibility of deep learning approaches to enhance oral health outcomes.

Keywords: Oral Health; Cavity Detection; Web Application Tool; CNN(Convolutional Neural Networks); Deep Learning

Wolfgang Maass, Veda C. Storey,
Pairing conceptual modeling with machine learning,
Data & Knowledge Engineering,
Volume 134,
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101909,
ISSN 0169-023X,
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(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0169023X21000367>)

Abstract: Both conceptual modeling and machine learning have long been recognized as important areas of research. With the increasing emphasis on digitizing and processing large amounts of data for business and other applications, it would be helpful to consider how these areas of research can complement each other. To understand how they can be paired, we provide an overview of machine learning foundations and development cycle. We then examine how conceptual modeling can be applied to machine learning and propose a framework for incorporating conceptual modeling into data science projects. The framework is illustrated by applying it to a healthcare application. For the inverse pairing, machine learning can impact conceptual modeling through text and rule mining, as well as knowledge graphs. The pairing of conceptual modeling and machine learning in this way should help lay the foundations for future research.

Keywords: Conceptual modeling; Machine learning; Methodologies and tools; Models; Database management; Framework for incorporating conceptual modeling into data science projects; Artificial intelligence

Lorenzo Malandri, Fabio Mercorio, Mario Mezzanzanica, Andrea Seveso,
Model-contrastive explanations through symbolic reasoning,
Decision Support Systems,
Volume 176,
2024,
114040,
ISSN 0167-9236,
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dss.2023.114040>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S016792362300115X>)

Abstract: Explaining how two machine learning classification models differ in their behaviour is gaining significance in eXplainable AI, given the increasing diffusion of learning-based decision support systems. Human decision-makers deal with more than one machine learning model in several practical situations. Consequently, the importance of understanding how two machine learning models work beyond their prediction performances is key to understanding their behaviour, differences, and likeness. Some attempts have been made to address these problems, for instance, by explaining text classifiers in a time-contrastive fashion. In this paper, we present MERLIN, a novel eXplainable AI approach that provides contrastive explanations of two machine learning models, introducing the concept of model-contrastive explanations. We propose an encoding that allows MERLIN to work with both text and tabular data and with mixed continuous and discrete features. To show the effectiveness of our approach, we evaluate it on an extensive set of benchmark datasets. MERLIN is also implemented as a python-pip package.

Keywords: eXplainable AI; Contrastive explanation methods for XAI; Post-hoc explainability; XAI Interpretability

Michael T. Lash,
HEX: Human-in-the-loop explainability via deep reinforcement learning,
Decision Support Systems,
Volume 187,
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114304,
ISSN 0167-9236,
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dss.2024.114304>.
(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0167923624001374>)

Abstract: The use of machine learning (ML) models in decision-making contexts, particularly those used in high-stakes decision-making, are fraught with issue and peril since a person – not a machine – must ultimately be held accountable for the consequences of decisions made using such systems. Machine learning explainability (MLX) promises to provide decision-makers with prediction-specific rationale, assuring them that the model-elicited predictions are made for the right reasons and are thus reliable. Few works explicitly consider this key human-in-the-loop (HITL) component, however. In this work we propose HEX, a human-in-the-loop deep reinforcement learning approach to MLX. HEX incorporates 0-distrust projection to synthesize decider-specific explainers that produce explanations strictly in terms of a decider's preferred explanatory features using any classification model. Our formulation explicitly considers the decision boundary of the ML model in question using a proposed explanatory point mode of explanation, thus ensuring explanations are specific to the ML model in question. We empirically evaluate HEX against other competing methods, finding that HEX is competitive with the state-of-the-art and outperforms other methods in human-in-the-loop scenarios. We conduct a randomized, controlled laboratory experiment utilizing actual explanations elicited from both HEX and competing methods. We causally establish that our method increases decider's trust and tendency to rely on trusted features.

Keywords: Explainability; Interpretability; Human-in-the-loop; Deep reinforcement learning; Machine learning; Behavioral machine learning; Decision support

Xinrui Zhang, Pincan Zhao, Jason Jaskolka,
Navigating the DevOps landscape,
Journal of Systems and Software,
Volume 223,
2025,
112331,
ISSN 0164-1212,
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jss.2024.112331>.
(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0164121224003753>)

Abstract: Context:

DevOps, with its increasing prevalence in both industry and academia, has evolved into various DevOps variants (namely XOps) to address emerging technological and operational challenges. However, this proliferation has created confusion and a lack of clarity about the systematic understanding of these XOps and their interrelationship in the DevOps landscape, leading to fragmented knowledge and application.

Objective:

This research seeks to construct a comprehensive picture of the existing DevOps landscape, clarifying the nature and nuances of various XOps, to guide effective future studies and implementations.

Method:

Utilizing Multivocal Literature Review (MLR), 80 gathered documents are thoroughly examined from throughout the whole community, encompassing both white and grey literature, to map the DevOps landscape.

Results:

Our review systematically discovered 38 XOps terms and 13 well-studied XOps including AIOps, BizDevOps, CloudOps, DataOps, DevSecOps, FinOps, GitOps, MLOps, ModelOps, NetDevOps, NoOps, SecDevOps and TwinOps. We provided dictionary-like resource that elucidates the core concepts and main ideas associated with each XOps. An in-depth understanding of intricate evolution from DevOps to XOps is delved into, supplemented by the research of relationships between XOps and various technological enablers as well as relationships between XOps and organizational teams, contributing to the ongoing dialogue surrounding their application and evolution.

Implications:

This paper provides a foundational understanding of the DevOps landscape including open issues and challenges, current and future trends, assisting both researchers and practitioners in navigating this complex field. It establishes a platform for further research and practical applications in the evolving field of DevOps and XOps.

Keywords: DevOps; Multivocal Literature Review; Research Roadmap

Yuming Li, Johnny Chan, Gabrielle Peko, David Sundaram,
An explanation framework and method for AI-based text emotion analysis and visualisation,
Decision Support Systems,

Volume 178,
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114121,
ISSN 0167-9236,
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dss.2023.114121>.

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Abstract: With the rapid development of artificial intelligence, there is an increasing number of industries relying on the accuracy and efficiency of deep learning algorithms. But due to the inexplicability and black box effect of deep neural networks, we can only obtain results without knowing the applied reasoning behind them. That engenders scepticism and resistance from some quarters of deep learning-based technologies. In the context of emotion analysis used in business and public opinion monitoring, it is sometimes difficult for decision-makers to trust the outcome without explanation from the supposedly emotionless machines. There are mathematical-based explanation methods, and they often generalise emotion analysis as a classification task. Still, emotion should be different from other task categories because the generation of emotion involves human-specific factors and logic. This paper proposes an emotion analysis explanation framework that is grounded in psychological theories focusing on the stimulus from classic emotion theories. This proposed framework emphasises considering the cause and trigger of emotions as the explanation for the deep learning-based emotion analysis, and it includes two main components: the extraction of the emotion cause and the visualisation of emotion-triggering words. Compared with the existing approaches, our proposed framework is based on the perspective of human psychology with higher credibility and significant theoretical support. In addition, we purposefully design and implement an intuitive visualisation for the framework, instead of complex numerical representations, to improve the explanation comprehensibility for a broader audience.

Keywords: Explainable AI; Explanation framework; Emotion analysis; Emotion theory

Tanvir H Sardar, Showkat A. Dar, Jitendra Jaiswal, Guru Prasad M S, Mudit Mittal, Vikash Kumar,
Enhancing Security in MANETs with Deep Learning-Based Intrusion Detection,
Procedia Computer Science,
Volume 259,
2025,
Pages 120-129,
ISSN 1877-0509,
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2025.03.313>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877050925010579>)

Abstract: Mobile Ad-hoc Networks (MANETs) are dynamic, collaborative networks that maintain reliable connections in a self-organised manner. Intermediate nodes forward data packets between source and destination nodes. However, these nodes are prone to attacks, making intrusion detection systems critical. This paper presents a deep learning algorithm called Graph Neural Network (GNN) to detect possible intrusions in nodes. The GNN is trained with various datasets and tested on the network, due to the mobile nature of MANET nodes, network traffic increases, heightening the risk of unauthorised disruptions. The proposed method is computed using the NS2 simulation tool and shows better resilience to attacks than methods like AODV, ANFIS, and GOA-SVM. The proposed system achieves a Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR) of 90.53%, while AODV, ANFIS, and GOA-SVM achieve 89.13%, 87.69%, and 87.32% respectively for 100 nodes. The method is compared with existing methods in terms of PDR and end-to-end delay during training and testing phases.

Keywords: Graph Neural Network (GNN); Intrusion Detection; Mobile Ad-hoc Networks (MANETs); NS2 Simulation Tool; Packet Delivery Ratio (PDR)

Sanaa Kaddoura, Abdu Gumaei,
Towards effective and efficient online exam systems using deep learning-based cheating detection approach,
Intelligent Systems with Applications,
Volume 16,
2022,
200153,
ISSN 2667-3053,
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.iswa.2022.200153>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2667305322000904>)

Abstract: With the high growth of digitization and globalization, online exam systems continue to gain popularity and stretch, especially in the case of spreading infections like a pandemic. Cheating detection in online exam systems is a significant and necessary task to maintain the integrity of the exam and give unbiased, fair results. Currently, online exam systems use vision-based traditional machine learning (ML) methods and provide examiners with tools to detect cheating throughout the exam. However, conventional ML methods depend on handcrafted features and cannot learn the hierarchical representations of objects from data itself, affecting the efficiency and effectiveness of such systems. The proposed research aims to develop an effective and efficient approach for online exam systems that uses deep learning models for real-time cheating detection from recorded video frames and speech. The developed approach includes three essential modules, which constantly estimate the critical behavior of the candidate student. These modules are the front camera-based cheating detection module, the back camera-based cheating detection module, and the speech-based detection module. It can classify and detect whether the candidate is cheating during the exam by automatically extracting useful features from visual images and speech through deep convolutional neural networks (CNNs) and the Gaussian-based discrete Fourier transform (DFT) statistical method. We

evaluate our system using a public dataset containing recorded audio and video data samples collected from different subjects carrying out several types of cheating in online exams. These collected data samples are used to obtain the experimental results and demonstrate the proposed work's efficiency and effectiveness.

Keywords: Deep convolutional neural networks; Cheating detection; Video frames; Speech; Soft voting decision fusion; Gaussian-based discrete Fourier transform

Bilal Sowan, Li Zhang, Essam H. Houssein, Hazem Qattous, Mohammad Azzeh, Bayan Massad,

DOVE-FELM: A fusion-optimized feature selection and heterogeneous ensemble learning framework for early prediction of chronic kidney disease risk,

Array,

Volume 28,

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100613,

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.array.2025.100613>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2590005625002401>)

Abstract: Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD) affects over 800 million individuals worldwide, yet existing prediction models deliver suboptimal performance on imbalanced datasets and lack clinical interpretability for early detection. This study presents DOVE-FELM, a framework that integrates Diverse Optimization Voting Ensemble (DOVE) with Fusion Ensemble Learning Model (FELM) for early-stage CKD risk prediction. DOVE employs consensus-based feature selection through eight heterogeneous optimization algorithms and incorporates a Symptom-Weighted and Influenced Patient Network (SWIPN) to capture patient-symptom connectivity patterns. FELM combines Random Forest and REPTree classifiers through adaptive weighting optimized via meta-level learning. The framework was validated on six imbalanced medical datasets (imbalance ratios from 1.67:1 to 29.06:1) through 10-fold stratified cross-validation. Specifically, evaluated using the UCI CKD dataset, DOVE-FELM achieved 99.75%, 99.8%, 99.8%, 99.8%, and 0.9947 for accuracy, AUC, sensitivity, specificity, and Cohen's Kappa scores, respectively. The Wilcoxon signed-rank test further ascertains statistical significance of the proposed model over nine baseline methods. Also, external validation on the Tawam Hospital CKD dataset with an imbalance ratio of 7.77:1, yielded an accuracy rate of 95.19%. Cross-disease validation on thyroid disease, thoracic surgery, cervical cancer, and AIDS clinical trials datasets demonstrated consistent performance (96.80–99.71% accuracy). Feature dimensionality reduction of 70.8% (24 → 7 biomarkers) enhanced clinical interpretability. DOVE-FELM advances computational frameworks for early chronic disease prediction through the integration of optimization-based feature selection with clinical domain knowledge. It shows strong potential for application in population-scale screening programs.

Keywords: DOVE-FELM framework; Optimization-based feature selection; Heterogeneous ensemble model; Clinical knowledge integration; Chronic kidney disease prediction

Nikolas Stege, Michael H. Breitner,

Insights into commonalities of a sample: A visualization framework to explore unusual subset-dataset relationships,

Data & Knowledge Engineering,

Volume 151,

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102299,

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.datak.2024.102299>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0169023X24000235>)

Abstract: Domain experts are driven by business needs, while data analysts develop and use various algorithms, methods, and tools, but often without domain knowledge. A major challenge for companies and organizations is to integrate data analytics in business processes and workflows. We deduce an interactive process and visualization framework to enable value creating collaboration in inter- and cross-disciplinary teams. Domain experts and data analysts are both empowered to analyze and discuss results and come to well-founded insights and implications. Inspired by a typical auditing problem, we develop and apply a visualization framework to single out unusual data in general subsets for potential further investigation. Our framework is applicable to both unusual data detected manually by domain experts or by algorithms applied by data analysts. Application examples show typical interaction, collaboration, visualization, and decision support.

Keywords: Data visualization; Visual analytics; Commonality plots; Subset-dataset relationships; Anomaly explanation; Decision support

Kai Heinrich, Patrick Zschech, Christian Janiesch, Markus Bonin,

Process data properties matter: Introducing gated convolutional neural networks (GCNN) and key-value-predict attention networks (KVP) for next event prediction with deep learning,

Decision Support Systems,

Volume 143,

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113494,

ISSN 0167-9236,

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dss.2021.113494>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S016792362100004X>)

Abstract: Predicting next events in predictive process monitoring enables companies to manage and control processes at an early stage and reduce their action distance. In recent years, approaches have steadily moved from classical statistical methods towards the application of deep neural network architectures, which outperform the former and enable analysis without explicit knowledge of the underlying process model. While the focus of prior research was on the long short-term memory network architecture, more deep learning architectures offer promising extensions that have proven useful for other applications of sequential data. In our work, we introduce a gated convolutional neural network and a key-value-predict attention network to the task of next event prediction. In a comprehensive evaluation study on 11 real-life benchmark datasets, we show that these two novel architectures surpass prior work in 34 out of 44 metric-dataset combinations. For our evaluation, we consider the effects of process data properties, such as sparsity, variation, and repetitiveness, and discuss their impact on the prediction quality of the different deep learning architectures. Similarly, we evaluate their classification properties in terms of generalization and handling class imbalance. Our results provide guidance for researchers and practitioners alike on how to select, validate, and comprehensively benchmark (novel) predictive process monitoring models. In particular, we highlight the importance of sufficiently diverse process data properties in event logs and the comprehensive reporting of multiple performance indicators to achieve meaningful results.

Keywords: Process mining; Predictive process monitoring; Machine learning; Deep learning; Gated convolutional neural network; Key-value-predict attention network

Mengming Michael Dong, Theophanis C. Stratopoulos, Victor Xiaoqi Wang,

A scoping review of ChatGPT research in accounting and finance,

International Journal of Accounting Information Systems,

Volume 55,

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100715,

ISSN 1467-0895,

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.accinf.2024.100715>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1467089524000484>)

Abstract: This paper provides a review of recent publications and working papers on ChatGPT and related Large Language Models (LLMs) in accounting and finance. The aim is to understand the current state of research in these two areas and identify potential research opportunities for future inquiry. We identify three common themes from these earlier studies. The first theme focuses on applications of ChatGPT and LLMs in various fields of accounting and finance. The second theme utilizes ChatGPT and LLMs as a new research tool by leveraging their capabilities such as classification, summarization, and text generation. The third theme investigates implications of LLM adoption for accounting and finance professionals, as well as for various organizations and sectors. While these earlier studies provide valuable insights, they leave many important questions unanswered or partially addressed. We propose venues for further exploration and provide technical guidance for researchers seeking to employ ChatGPT and related LLMs as a tool for their research.

Keywords: ChatGPT; Generative AI; LLMs; Audit; Financial reporting; Tax; AIS; Asset pricing; Corporate finance

Nader Elsayed,

Strategic AI disclosures and legitimacy: Impression management in UK FTSE100 annual reports,

International Journal of Accounting Information Systems,

Volume 56,

2025,

100757,

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.accinf.2025.100757>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1467089525000338>)

Abstract: By incorporating impression management strategies with legitimacy theory, this study investigates how UK FTSE100 corporations strategically communicate their AI disclosures to achieve, sustain, and/or restore legitimacy. It employs a mixed-methods content analysis to analyse textual AI data from the annual reports of 80 UK non-financial corporations listed in the FTSE100 index (2020 to 2023). Results reveal an increasing trend among UK corporations to disclose AI narratives. This study finds that FTSE100 corporations employ a blend of 'assertive' and 'defensive' impression management tactics in AI disclosures to influence stakeholder perceptions and maintain their legitimacy. Findings also indicate a significant post-crisis shift from defensive to assertive AI disclosures, underscoring how FTSE100 corporations strategically adapted their impression management tactics to reinforce pragmatic, moral, and cognitive legitimacy. This study contributes to the literature by demonstrating how impression-management tactics shape AI legitimacy, offering practitioners strategies for transparent communication, informing legislators on ethical AI regulation, and enabling stakeholders to interpret AI disclosures as indicators of corporate conduct.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence Disclosures; Legitimacy Theory; Impression Management; Mixed-Methods Content Analysis; FTSE100 Corporations

Yu Tian, Wencheng Wang,

Enhance Customer Experience in the Digital Economy with Advanced Neural Network Technology and Big Data Analytics,

Procedia Computer Science,

Volume 262,

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ISSN 1877-0509,

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2025.05.056>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1877050925019039>)

Abstract: In the context of the digital economy, enterprises are facing the challenges of fierce market competition and increasingly diverse customer needs, so this paper will discuss how to improve the customer experience of enterprises in the digital economy based on the use of neural network technology and big data analysis. Based on accurate data analysis, companies can identify potential churned customers, optimize personalized services, and improve customer satisfaction. The study shows that after the application of technology, the satisfaction of all customer groups has increased significantly, especially the potential churn customer group, whose satisfaction has increased by 32.20%. In addition, the number of complaints from the loyal customer group has completely disappeared, further verifying the effectiveness of technology in improving service quality. The specific data also shows that the increase of customer loyalty in the first-time experience customers and potential churn customer groups reached 22.22% and 29.82% respectively. As a result, neural networks and big data technologies provide strong support for enterprises, significantly reducing customer complaints and increasing customer loyalty. It can be seen that this system is based on accurate personalized service and intelligent analysis, which can effectively enhance the market competitiveness of enterprises and promote enterprises to stand out in the fiercely competitive environment.

Keywords: Neural Network Technology; Digital Economy; Customer Experience; Hoist; Big Data Analytics

Md Ismail Hossain Siddiqui, Shakil Khan, Zishad Hossain Limon, Hamdadur Rahman, Mahbub Alam Khan, Abdullah Al Sakib, S M Masfequier Rahman Swapno, Rezaul Haque, Ahmed Wasif Reza, Abhishek Appaji,

Accelerated and accurate cervical cancer diagnosis using a novel stacking ensemble method with explainable AI,

Informatics in Medicine Unlocked,

Volume 56,

2025,

101657,

ISSN 2352-9148,

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.imu.2025.101657>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2352914825000450>)

Abstract: Cervical cancer is a preventable yet life-threatening disease that claims hundreds of thousands of lives each year, particularly in low-resource settings where timely screening is scarce. Current Deep Learning (DL) approaches for automated cervical cytology classification encounter challenges such as class imbalance, computational inefficiency, and inadequate generalizability. This study proposes a novel CerviXEnsemble model that integrates multiple pre-trained DL architectures (Inception-ResNetV2, EfficientNet-B6, ResNet152, Inception-ResNetV2, EfficientNet-B6, DenseNet201, and NASNetMobile) as base learners, along with a dense-layer meta-learner that refines and consolidates predictions for improved robustness. Unlike traditional single-CNN models, our stacking ensemble approach utilizes diverse feature representations to enhance classification stability and generalization across multiple cytology datasets. To validate the model, we experimented with the Herlev and SIPaKMeD benchmark datasets in this study. Techniques like contrast enhancement and data augmentation were employed to optimize feature extraction. The model achieved state-of-the-art performance, attaining an accuracy of 99.38 % and an F1-score of 98.49 % on the Herlev dataset and an accuracy of 98.71 % and an F1-score of 97.53 % on SIPaKMeD. These performances are superior to previous studies in controlling class imbalance and providing stable predictions over different samples. Additionally, Explainable AI (XAI) techniques were incorporated to ensure transparent and interpretable predictions, aiding clinicians in their decision-making processes. An interpretable web application was developed for real-time Pap smear analysis to reduce the diagnostic workload for pathologists by identifying high-risk samples. This solution shows great promise for use in various healthcare settings, maintaining high diagnostic accuracy while requiring minimal computational resources, making it suitable for both urban hospitals and rural clinics.

Keywords: Cervical cancer; Explainable AI; Pap smear image analysis; Diagnostic tool; Ensemble learning

Divish Rengasamy, Jimiama M. Mase, Aayush Kumar, Benjamin Rothwell, Mercedes Torres Torres, Morgan R. Alexander, David A. Winkler, Graziela P. Figueredo,

Feature importance in machine learning models: A fuzzy information fusion approach,

Neurocomputing,

Volume 511,

2022,

Pages 163-174,

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neucom.2022.09.053>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0925231222011584>)

Abstract: With the widespread use of machine learning to support decision-making, it is increasingly important to verify and understand the reasons why a particular output is produced. Although post-training feature importance approaches assist this interpretation, there is an overall lack of consensus regarding how feature importance should be quantified, making explanations of model predictions unreliable. In addition, many of these explanations depend on the specific machine learning approach employed and on the subset of data used when calculating feature importance. A possible solution to improve the reliability of explanations is to combine results from multiple feature importance quantifiers from different machine learning approaches coupled with re-sampling. Current state-of-the-art ensemble feature importance fusion uses crisp techniques to fuse results from different approaches. There is, however, significant loss of information as these approaches are not context-aware and reduce several quantifiers to a single crisp output. More importantly, their representation of “importance” as coefficients may be difficult to comprehend by end-users and decision makers. Here we show how the use of fuzzy data fusion methods can overcome some of the important limitations of crisp fusion methods by making the importance of features easily understandable.

Keywords: Feature importance; Fuzzy systems; Information fusion; Interpretability; Machine learning; Responsible AI

Raghu Raman, Debidutta Pattnaik, Laurie Hughes, Prema Nedungadi,
Unveiling the dynamics of AI applications: A review of reviews using scientometrics and BERTopic modeling,
Journal of Innovation & Knowledge,
Volume 9, Issue 3,
2024,
100517,
ISSN 2444-569X,
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jik.2024.100517>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2444569X24000568>)

Abstract: In a world that has rapidly transformed through the advent of artificial intelligence (AI), our systematic review, guided by the PRISMA protocol, investigates a decade of AI research, revealing insights into its evolution and impact. Our study, examining 3,767 articles, has drawn considerable attention, as evidenced by an impressive 63,577 citations, underscoring the scholarly community's profound engagement. Our study reveals a collaborative landscape with 18,189 contributing authors, reflecting a robust network of researchers advancing AI and machine learning applications. Review categories focus on systematic reviews and bibliometric analyses, indicating an increasing emphasis on comprehensive literature synthesis and quantitative analysis. The findings also suggest an opportunity to explore emerging methodologies such as topic modeling and meta-analysis. We dissect the state of the art presented in these reviews, finding themes throughout the broad scholarly discourse through thematic clustering and BERTopic modeling. Categorization of study articles across fields of research indicates dominance in Information and Computing Sciences, followed by Biomedical and Clinical Sciences. Subject categories reveal interconnected clusters across various sectors, notably in healthcare, engineering, business intelligence, and computational technologies. Semantic analysis via BERTopic revealed nineteen clusters mapped to themes such as AI in health innovations, AI for sustainable development, AI and deep learning, AI in education, and ethical considerations. Future research directions are suggested, emphasizing the need for intersectional bias mitigation, holistic health approaches, AI's role in environmental sustainability, and the ethical deployment of generative AI.

Keywords: Thematic analysis; Cocitation analysis; Topic modeling; BERTopic; Artificial intelligence; Sustainable development goal; Cybersecurity; Innovation; Ethics; Blockchain

Afonso Lobo, Daniel Sá, João Cunha, Ricardo Duarte, Júlio Duarte, Manuel Filipe Santos,
Healthcare Cognitive Decision Support System – The State-of-the-Art,
Procedia Computer Science,
Volume 257,
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Abstract: Cognitive decision support systems promise to take the quality of decision-making to the next level. These systems, which can be applied to a variety of contexts, hold great potential for revolutionizing the decision-making process in the healthcare field. This study aims to raise awareness of this type of system and identify the current state of knowledge about them. A literature review was carried out, explaining the associated fundamental concepts and AI strands, presenting related studies already carried out in the field, and identifying the associated research gap.

Keywords: Cognitive Decision Support Systems; Healthcare; Decision-Making; Artificial Intelligence

M.A. Bouzinier, D. Etin, S.I. Trifonov, V.N. Evdokimova, V. Ulitin, J. Shen, A. Kokorev, A.A. Ghazani, Y. Chekaluk, Z. Albertyn, A. Giersch, C.C. Morton, F. Abraamyan, P.K. Bendapudi, S. Sunyaev, Undiagnosed Diseases Network, Brigham Genomic Medicine, SEQuencing a Baby for an Optimal Outcome, Quantori, J.B. Krier,
AnFiSA: An open-source computational platform for the analysis of sequencing data for rare genetic disease,
Journal of Biomedical Informatics,
Volume 133,
2022,
104174,
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Abstract: Despite genomic sequencing rapidly transforming from being a bench-side tool to a routine procedure in a hospital, there is a noticeable lack of genomic analysis software that supports both clinical and research workflows as well as crowdsourcing. Furthermore, most existing software packages are not forward-compatible in regards to supporting ever-changing diagnostic rules adopted by the genetics community. Regular updates of genomics databases pose challenges for reproducible and traceable automated genetic diagnostics tools. Lastly, most of the software tools score low on explainability amongst clinicians. We have created a fully open-source variant curation tool, AnFiSA, with the intention to invite and accept contributions from clinicians, researchers, and professional software developers. The design of AnFiSA addresses the

forementioned issues via the following architectural principles: using a multidimensional database management system (DBMS) for genomic data to address reproducibility, curated decision trees adaptable to changing clinical rules, and a crowdsourcing-friendly interface to address difficult-to-diagnose cases. We discuss how we have chosen our technology stack and describe the design and implementation of the software. Finally, we show in detail how selected workflows can be implemented using the current version of AnFiSA by a medical geneticist.

Keywords: Clinical genomics; Genome sequencing; Genome annotation; Genome filtering; Diagnostic clinical genomics; OLAP; Explainable models

Sarah Bankins, Stefan Jooss, Simon Lloyd D. Restubog, Mauricio Marrone, Anna Carmella Ocampo, Mindy Shoss,
Navigating career stages in the age of artificial intelligence: A systematic interdisciplinary review and agenda for future research,
Journal of Vocational Behavior,
Volume 153,
2024,
104011,
ISSN 0001-8791,
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Abstract: As artificial intelligence (AI) use expands within organizations, its influence is increasingly permeating careers and vocational domains. However, there is a notable lack of structured insights regarding AI's role in shaping individual career paths across career stages. To address this gap, we undertook a systematic literature review of 104 empirical articles, aiming to synthesize the scholarship on AI in the context of careers. Drawing upon career stage theory, we examine the implications of AI on careers, identify key barriers and enablers of AI use in this area, and reveal how the utilization of AI impacts individuals' career competencies. In doing so, we illustrate how AI actively shapes individuals' career trajectories and we dissect these effects both within and across various career stages to situate AI within the broader context of careers research. Adopting a sustainable career lens, we conclude by outlining a future research agenda that advocates for the design and adoption of AI systems that promote sustainable and equitable careers.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence; Careers; Career stages; Vocational services; Future of work; Sustainable careers

Abebe Diro, Shahriar Kaiser, Akanksha Saini, Samar Fatima, Pham Cong Hiep, Fikadu Erba,
Workplace security and privacy implications in the GenAI age: A survey,
Journal of Information Security and Applications,
Volume 89,
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103960,
ISSN 2214-2126,
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Abstract: Generative Artificial Intelligence (GenAI) is transforming the workplace, but its adoption introduces significant risks to data security and privacy. Recent incidents underscore the urgency of addressing these issues. This comprehensive survey investigates the implications of GenAI integration in workplaces, focusing on its impact on organizational operations and security. We analyze vulnerabilities within GenAI systems, threats they face, and repercussions of AI-driven workplace monitoring. By examining diverse attack vectors like model attacks and automated cyberattacks, we expose their potential to undermine data integrity and privacy. Unlike previous works, this survey specifically focuses on the security and privacy implications of GenAI within workplace settings, addressing issues like employee monitoring, deepfakes, and regulatory compliance. We delve into emerging threats during model training and usage phases, proposing countermeasures such as differential privacy for training data and robust authentication for access control. Additionally, we provide a comprehensive analysis of evolving regulatory frameworks governing AI tools globally. Based on our comprehensive analysis, we propose targeted recommendations for future research and policy-making to promote responsible and secure adoption of GenAI in the workplace, such as incentivizing the development of explainable AI (XAI) and establishing clear guidelines for ethical data usage. This survey equips stakeholders with a comprehensive understanding of GenAI's complex workplace landscape, empowering them to harness its benefits responsibly while mitigating risks.

Keywords: Cybersecurity; Generative AI; ChatGPT; Bard; Privacy; Security; Ethics

Tim Kreuzer, Panagiotis Papapetrou, Jelena Zdravkovic,
Artificial intelligence in digital twins—A systematic literature review,
Data & Knowledge Engineering,
Volume 151,
2024,
102304,
ISSN 0169-023X,
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.datak.2024.102304>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0169023X24000284>)

Abstract: Artificial intelligence and digital twins have become more popular in recent years and have seen usage across different application domains for various scenarios. This study reviews the literature at the intersection of the two fields, where digital twins integrate an artificial intelligence component. We follow a systematic literature review approach, analyzing a total of 149 related studies. In the assessed literature, a variety of problems are approached with an artificial intelligence-integrated digital twin, demonstrating its applicability across different fields. Our findings indicate that there is a lack of in-depth modeling approaches regarding the digital twin, while many articles focus on the implementation and testing of the artificial intelligence component. The majority of publications do not demonstrate a virtual-to-physical connection between the digital twin and the real-world system. Further, only a small portion of studies base their digital twin on real-time data from a physical system, implementing a physical-to-virtual connection.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence; Digital twin; Machine learning; Literature review; Business intelligence; Data mining

Rajat Kumar Behera, Marijn Janssen, Nripendra P. Rana, Pradip Kumar Bala, Debarun Chakraborty,

Responsible metaverse: Ethical metaverse principles for guiding decision-making and maintaining complex relationships for businesses in 3D virtual spaces,

Decision Support Systems,

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114337,

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(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0167923624001702>)

Abstract: A metaverse is a three-dimensional virtual space (3D VS) where businesses and individuals worldwide can engage, interact, communicate, transact, and exchange information in real-time through an immersive and collaborative platform. These interactions can create complex relationships influenced by the decision-making processes of businesses. Such complexity can lead to challenges in maintaining relationships, ensuring exclusiveness, preventing misuse, and addressing other ethical issues. Therefore, this study aims to identify ethical principles within the metaverse to guide decision-making and maintain complex relationships between users and businesses. Both qualitative and quantitative data were collected for analysis, and simple random sampling was employed for primary data collection. The empirical analysis was conducted using a mixed-method approach. The study identified four ethical principles that guide complex relationships within the metaverse: business benefit evaluation, fairness, explainability, and reliability principles. These principles positively influence decision-making, which, in turn, positively affects the maintenance of complex relationships within 3D VS.

Keywords: Metaverse; Responsible metaverse; Ethical decision-making; Ethical principles; 3D virtual spaces; Complex relationships

Mohammad Sadegh Khorshidi, José M. Merigó, Ghassan Beydoun,

Half a Century of Information Processing & Management: A bibliometric retrospective,

Information Processing & Management,

Volume 62, Issue 6,

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104238,

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ipm.2025.104238>.

(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0306457325001797>)

Abstract: Established in 1963 under the title Information Storage and Retrieval, the journal adopted its current name, Information Processing & Management (IPM), in 1975, reflecting a broadening scope aligned with computational and cognitive developments in information science. This study uses data from Web of Science and Scopus databases to deliver a longitudinal, multi-perspective bibliometric and science mapping analysis of IPM's evolution from 1963 to 2023. Employing co-citation analysis, bibliographic coupling, keyword co-occurrence, and thematic mapping via VOSviewer and Bibliometrix, the analysis delineates the structural, conceptual, and topical transformation of the journal content. Co-citation networks uncover foundational cores in information retrieval, relevance theory, and evaluation methodologies, while also revealing temporal shifts toward natural language processing, deep learning, and social media analytics. Bibliographic coupling identifies coherent intellectual clusters centered on GNN-based recommendation systems, blockchain-secured infrastructures, and sentiment-aware retrieval frameworks. Keyword co-occurrence and topic evolution trajectories illustrate the journal's recent pivot toward transformer models, misinformation detection, ethical AI, and interdisciplinary convergence across cognitive science, machine learning, and computational linguistics. Regional co-word analysis underscores epistemological diversity and geographic differentiation across North America, Europe, and East Asia. Productivity and influence metrics highlight the ascent of East Asian institutions and the emergence of globally distributed citation impact. Finally, SciVal-based topic and topic cluster analyses reveal the journal's role in advancing highly cited research (as measured by FWCI) in areas such as ABSA, multi-view clustering, and health informatics. This work not only charts IPM's conceptual landscape and disciplinary diffusion but also provides actionable intelligence on the journal's strategic positioning within the broader information and computational sciences.

Keywords: Information Processing; Management; Bibliometrics; Web of Science; Scopus; VOS viewer

Usharani Hareesh Govindarajan, Gagan Narang, Dhiraj Kumar Singh, Vinay Surendra Yadav,

Blockchain technologies adoption in healthcare: Overcoming barriers amid the hype cycle to enhance patient care,

Technological Forecasting and Social Change,

Volume 213,

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124031,
ISSN 0040-1625,
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2025.124031>.
(<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0040162525000629>)

Abstract: Blockchain technologies are increasingly recognized as a transformative force across industries, offering potential solutions for information management, data security, and operational efficiency improvement. However, integration into the healthcare sector faces significant barriers, ranging from technical challenges to organizational resistance. In this study, a methodology is proposed that examines these critical barriers through a comprehensive analysis of 3265 academic papers and derives actionable solutions from 1566 patents published between 2016 and 2023. This approach bridges the gap between identifying challenges and implementing solutions. Using the “Stepwise Weight Assessment Ratio Analysis (SWARA)”, twelve critical adoption challenges are analyzed, while Top2Vec-based topic modeling identifies innovations that best address the ranked barriers. In addition to this, the proposed ‘healthcare ecosphere’ knowledge map serves as a comprehensive tool to analyze key stakeholders, their interactions, and the alignment of adoption barriers in solution spaces. The findings show that innovations in blockchain technologies are heavily concentrated in areas such as data security and application functionalities, whereas other critical domains—such as consensus mechanisms, governance, and regulatory frameworks—remain underexplored, pointing to opportunities for growth and development. The mapping of barriers to solutions provides practical guidance for healthcare providers, policymakers, and technologists seeking to implement the blockchain technologies effectively.

Keywords: Adoption barriers; Blockchain technologies; Healthcare ecosphere; Patent analysis; SWARA; Top2Vec

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Understanding dark side of artificial intelligence (AI) integrated business analytics: assessing firm's operational inefficiency and competitiveness	Shahriar Akter, Sheshadri Chatterjee, Yogesh K Dwivedi, Nripendra P Rana	European Journal of Information Systems	31	3	p364 - p387	2022	10.1080/0960085x.2021.1955628	#####	https://doi.org/10.1080/0960085x.2021.1955628	64644	324
Harnessing uncertainty: a new approach to real estate investment decision support	Are Oust, Arne Johan Pollestad	Quantitative Finance	25	11	p1771 - p1788	2025	10.1080/014697688.2025.2468269	#####	https://doi.org/10.1080/014697688.2025.2468269	1664	1
AI and the decision-making process: a literature review in healthcare, financial, and technology sectors	Sadi Alawadi, Imad BaniHani, Nadia Elmrayyan	Journal of Decision Systems	33	sup1		2024	10.1080/012460125.2024.2349425	#####	https://doi.org/10.1080/012460125.2024.2349425	7039	18
Tell me more, tell me more: the impact of explanations on learning from feedback provided by Artificial Intelligence	Hanna R Broder, Marie C Fahr, Lior Fink, Maximilian FÄrster, Mathias Klier	European Journal of Information Systems	34	2	p323 - p345	2025	10.1080/0960085x.2024.2404028	#####	https://doi.org/10.1080/0960085x.2024.2404028	5555	7
A bibliometric analysis insights into the intellectual dynamics of artificial intelligence for the micro, small, and medium enterprises	Noptanit Chotisarn, Thadathibesra Phuthong	Cogent Business & Management	12	1		2025	10.1080/023311975.2025.2491684	17-Apr-25	https://doi.org/10.1080/023311975.2025.2491684	4878	13

Emerging technologies in finance: challenges for a sustainable finance	Sana Jellouli, Dhouha Nefla	Cogent Business & Management	12	1		2025	10.1080/23311975.2025.2495191	#####	https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2025.2495191	9093	15
Merged LSTM-MLP for option valuation	Christian O Ewald, Rita Pimentel, Morten Risstad, Erlend Stegavik Rygg, Jacob Vinje, Sjur Westgaard, Cassandra Wu	Quantitative Finance	25	11	p1679 - p1694	2025	10.1080/14697688.2025.2493965	#####	https://doi.org/10.1080/14697688.2025.2493965	2183	1
In-depth analysis of organisational structures for digital twin ecosystems	José Barbosa, Paulo Leitao, Victória Melo, Flávia Pires, Fernando de la Prieta	Production & Manufacturing Research	13	1		2025	10.1080/21693277.2025.2591786	#####	https://doi.org/10.1080/21693277.2025.2591786	741	2
Artificial intelligence enriched industry 4.0 readiness in manufacturing: the extended CCMS2.0e maturity model	Tamás Járvis, Tibor Kovács, Andrea Ká, Gábor Nick, Károly Pocsarovszky, Klaudia Zeleny	Production & Manufacturing Research	12	1		2024	10.1080/21693277.2024.2357683	20-Jun-24	https://doi.org/10.1080/21693277.2024.2357683	2375	9
Artificial intelligence research in organizations: a bibliometric approach	Yangjie Lai, Dege Liu, Peng Liu	Cogent Business & Management	11	1		2024	10.1080/23311975.2024.2408439	#####	https://doi.org/10.1080/23311975.2024.2408439	2517	9
Recent evolution and growth of AI and advanced technologies in accounting and finance: systematic review and bibliometric analysis	Ventura Castillo-Ramos, Juan Manuel Corchado, Javier Parra Dominguez, Laura Sanz Martn, Elisabeth Zafra-Gmez, José L Zafra-Gmez	Spanish Journal of Finance and Accounting / Revista Española de Financiación y Contabilidad	55	1	p47 - p88	2026	10.1080/02102412.2025.2582120	#####	https://doi.org/10.1080/02102412.2025.2582120	4962	2
Design principles for artificial intelligence-augmented decision making: An action design research study	Savindu Herath Pathirannehelage, Yash Raj Shrestha, Georg von Krogh	European Journal of Information Systems	34	2	p207 - p229	2025	10.1080/0960085x.2024.2330402	#####	https://doi.org/10.1080/0960085x.2024.2330402	22573	52

Leverage Generative AI for human resource management: integrated risk analysis approach	Ziming Cai, Ying Jiang, Xiaojun Wang	The International Journal of Human Resource Management	36	11	p1929 - p1959	2025	10.1080/09585192.2025.2544972	#####	https://doi.org/10.1080/09585192.2025.2544972	10376	9
Digital supply chain surveillance using artificial intelligence: definitions, opportunities and risks	Alexandra Brintrup, Guven Demirel, Edward Kosasih, Bart L MacCarthy, Philipp Schaffer, Ge Zheng	International Journal of Production Research	62	13	p4674 - p4695	2024	10.1080/0/00207543.2023.2270719	#####	https://doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2023.2270719	15839	61
A review of port state control inspections: critical issues and emerging trends in maritime oversight	Mohan Anantharaman, Rabiul Islam, Hong-Oanh Nguyen, Abubakar Mahmud Sheriff	Australian Journal of Maritime & Ocean Affairs			p1 - p23	5187	10.1080/0/18366503.2025.2554348	#####	https://doi.org/10.1080/18366503.2025.2554348	2933	1
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Understanding data professionals in the police: a qualitative study of system-level bureaucrats	Isabelle Fest, Albert Meijer, Mirko Schäfer, Jos van Dijck	Public Management Review	25	9	p1664 - p1684	2023	10.1080/14719037.2023.222734	15-Jun-23	https://doi.org/10.1080/14719037.2023.222734	5555	16
The influence of artificial intelligence quality on business-to-business relationships on E-commerce platforms: unveiling the nexus	Hassan Kalantari Daronkola, Alireza Nazarian, Ali Sarhadi, Mohammadjavad Shabankareh, Park Thaichon	International Journal of Advertising	44	8	p1483 - p1522	2025	10.1080/0487.2025.2557053	#####	https://doi.org/10.1080/0487.2025.2557053	4053	5
Towards resilient and viable supply chains: a multidimensional model and empirical analysis	Dmitry Ivanov, Antonio Padovano	International Journal of Production Research	63	17	p6252 - p6290	2025	10.1080/07543.2025.2470350	#####	https://doi.org/10.1080/07543.2025.2470350	8664	30
Reinforcement learning based dispatching solutions in semiconductor manufacturing: a literature review on validation and deployment	Thomas Altenmüller, Sebastian Feudel, Martin Gebser, Niels Hayen, Fin Higgins, Alessandro Immordino, Konstantin Schekotihin, Georg Seidel, Patrick Stöckermann, Marc Wegmann	Production & Manufacturing Research	13	1		2025	10.1080/03277.2025.2582472	#####	https://doi.org/10.1080/03277.2025.2582472	1413	0
Neuromarketing algorithms' consumer privacy and ethical considerations: challenges and opportunities	Irene Aliagas, Luis Manuel Cerdeja, Marcus Goncalves, Yiwei Hu	Cogent Business & Management	11	1		2024	10.1080/01975.2024.2333063	04-Apr-24	https://doi.org/10.1080/01975.2024.2333063	16322	45